

**MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES MODELLING OF CRUDE OIL PRICE, STOCK
MARKET MOVEMENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH NEXUS IN NIGERIA**

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FEBRUARY 2016

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BY

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OF MATHEMATICS AND STATISTICS,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE**

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FOR THE AWARD OF THE MASTER OF SCIENCE (M. Sc) DEGREE IN
STATISTICS**

FEBRUARY 2016

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “Multivariate Time Series Modelling of Crude Oil Price, Stock Market Movement and Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria” has been written by me and that it is the record of my own research work. It has not been presented in any previous application for a higher degree. All sources of information are specifically acknowledged using references.

Nsisong Patrick Ekong

February 2016

CERTIFICATION

This dissertation entitled “Multivariate Time Series Modelling of Crude Oil Price, Stock Market Movement and Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria” by Nsisong Patrick Ekong (12/PG/FS/ST/002) meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc) of the University of Uyo and is approved for its contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my parents, Chief and Mrs. Patrick Ekong Akpanobong.

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This work is a success as a result of direct and indirect contributions from a good number of people.

Firstly, I sincerely acknowledge the mighty hand of God in the entire process that resulted in this work. It is so obvious that it is only God that can do a thing like this and I say may His name alone be highly exalted in Jesus name, Amen.

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I pray the almighty God bless and reward all of you graciously in Jesus name, Amen.

ABSTRACT

This work seeks to model the dynamic relationships between crude oil price, stock market indicators and the economic growth in Nigeria using vector autoregressive (VAR) model and cointegration analysis. It also models the respective series as univariates and compares forecasts from the univariate model with those from the VAR model. Nigeria stock market capitalization and exchange rate (USD) are respectively used as proxies for stock market indicators and economic growth. The data sets are monthly data spanning from January 1995 to November 2014 and totaling up to 239 observations for each variable obtained from the United States Energy Information Agency (EIA), Nigerian Stock Market and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin respectively crude oil price, stock market capitalization and exchange rate. From the study, it is seen that ARIMA(0,1,1), ARIMA(3,1,1) and ARIMA(1,1,0) models are respectively the suitable models for crude oil price, stock market capitalization, and the exchange rate (USD). Furthermore, it is also observed that the dynamic relationships that exist among these variables can be captured with a vector autoregressive model of order three ($VAR(3)$) The structural inference carried out from the $VAR(3)$ model shows that the Nigerian stock market behavior and the economic growth can better be predicted when taking the past values of crude oil price into consideration. Finally, cointegration analysis was also used to uncover the long run relationships that exist among the series. Two cointegrating equations were found to exist among the variables. These results mean that the crude oil price, stock market movement and the economic growth have a long term and sustainable equilibrium relationship, and that stock market movement and the economic growth are affected by the distortions in the price of the crude oil.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The impacts of crude oil price shocks on economic variables have been a controversial but interesting topic globally over the past years. Controversial in the sense that, different and divergent results have been obtained amidst the dire need to curb the negative results of these oil price shocks on the economy. In an effort to unravel this, many researchers have used several measures in different dimensions to study this trend. All of which boil down to the fact that the impact of the oil price shocks varies from economy to economy depending on whether the economy is an importer of oil or an exporter of oil. As asserted by Marzieh¹ (2006) in Oriavwote and Eriemo² (2012), the magnitude of the direct effect of a given oil price increase depends on the share of the cost of oil in national income, the degree of dependence on imported oil and the ability of end-users to reduce their consumption and switch away from oil. For Nigerian economy, having oil as its main stay, the price of oil significantly shapes the economic status of the country.

The price of oil has witnessed significant fluctuations since 1995. For instance, it swings between \$17 per barrel and \$19 at different times in 1995 and about \$134 per barrel by June, 2008 where the distortions got to an all time peak. The oil price has fallen by more than 20% since June 2014, when it was \$106 a barrel. Recently, in the later part of November 2014, it was below \$70.

These distortions in the price of crude oil have been partly due to global oil demand, global financial crisis, OPEC regulations and foreign policies. And partly, as asserted by Oriavwote and Eriemo², (2012), the distortions is as a result of political unrest in the middle east, particularly, the revolutions in some Arab countries including Tunisia, Egypt, Libya, Yemen, and Syria as well as the Iranian nuclear crisis.

At a meeting in Vienna on November 27 2014 the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries, which controls nearly 40% of the world oil market, failed to reach agreement on production curbs, sending the price tumbling (Economist³, 2014). The oil price is also partly determined by actual supply and demand, and partly by expectation. Demand for energy is closely related to economic activity. Supply can be affected by weather (which prevents tankers loading) and by geopolitical upsets. If producers think the price is staying high, they invest, which after a lag boosts supply. Similarly, low prices lead to an investment drought. OPEC's decisions shape expectations: if it curbs supply sharply, it can send prices spiking. Saudi Arabia produces nearly 10m barrels a day—a third of the OPEC total. Four things are now affecting the picture. Demand is low because of weak economic activity, increased efficiency, and a growing switch away from oil to other fuels. Second, turmoil in Arab countries especially Iraq and Libya—two big oil producers with nearly 4m barrels a day combined. The market is more sanguine about geopolitical risk. Thirdly, America has become the world's largest oil producer. Though it does not export crude oil, it now imports much less, creating a lot of spare supply. Finally, the Saudis and their Gulf allies have decided not to sacrifice their own market share to restore the price. They could curb production sharply, but the main benefits would go to countries they detest such as Iran and Russia. Saudi Arabia can tolerate lower oil prices quite easily. It has \$900 billion in reserves. Its own oil costs very little (around \$5-6 per barrel) to drill out of the ground (Economist³, 2014).

Stock market, as a barometer of the economy, reflects the performance of companies and investments in the economy. Also known as the equity market, the stock market is a place in which shares of publicly held companies are issued and traded either through exchanges or over-the-counter markets. It is one of the most vital components of the free-market economy as it provides companies with access to capital in exchange for giving investors a sense of ownership in the company. The stock market plays a salient role in financial intermediation in both developed and developing countries in a way of utilizing the unused funds from the surplus units to fund the deficit units in the economy, a role that makes stock market a

medium of wealth redistribution. Depending largely on the market, share prices rise and fall and the market capitalization expanded at the stock exchange. They tend to rise or remain stable when companies or the economy in general show signs of stability, improvement and progression. This simultaneous movement of share prices and companies' performances makes stock market to be seen as an indicator of the general trend in the economy. When companies and the general economy is stable and with bigger prospects, large and long term capital resources are pooled through issuing of shares and stocks by industries in dire need of finance for expansion purposes. Thus, the overall development of the economy is a function of how well the stock market performs (Adaramola⁴, 2012). Empirical evidences from developed economies as well as the emerging markets have proved that the development of the stock market leads to economic growth (Asaolu and Ilo⁵, 2012).

Nigeria, a core oil-dependent economy, has crude oil as a major source of its revenue. It is estimated that over 90 percent of the total revenue in Nigeria accrue from petroleum and allied products and this makes the economy to be exposed to major crude oil price distortions. The economy having a very special feature of being both an exporter of crude oil and importer of refined petroleum products due to malfunctioning of refineries is even more vulnerable to oil price volatility. This oil price volatility is so severe that the Nigerian budget is even at some point in time tied up to a particular benchmark price of crude oil. The budget has been adjusted in so many occasions when there is a sudden change in crude oil prices such as the reduction of budget due to a fall in oil prices during the global financial crisis (Oriavwote and Eriemo², 2012).

The sudden negative distortions in the price of crude oil in the last and the first quarters of 2014 and 2015 respectively have raised panic in both oil exporting and oil dependent economies. In Nigeria particularly, economic activities and budgeting will be streamlined within the confines of this new oil price. Questions are raised on how to diversify the economy in a way of shifting our focus from oil as our main stay to other sectors like agriculture and manufacturing. Distortions in the international crude oil price affect both

exchange rate and inflation rates of an oil-dependent economy, this in-turn affect prospects of the economy for investors to invest and its direct consequence is reflected on the investability and returns of the stock market and the economy at large. As asserted by Golub⁶ (1983), a rise in oil prices could be viewed as a wealth transfer from oil importing countries to oil exporting ones. Increase in oil price tends to increase private disposable income in oil-exporting countries, this in-turn increases corporate profitability, raises domestic demand and stock prices thereby causing exchange rate to appreciate (Abdelaziz, Chortareas and Cipollini⁷, 2008). From the above assertions, it could be inferred that in oil exporting country, a positive distortion in the world oil prices improves the trade balance, leading to higher current account surplus and an improving and progressing net foreign asset position. These higher current account surplus and richer net foreign assets can then be channeled into bigger investments in stock markets, which in turn make way for higher returns. But the reverse is the case if the oil price decreases.

This relationship between the international crude oil price and the prospects of an oil-dependent economy is so interwoven such that disentangling them is almost impossible. If what causes the distortion in the world crude price could be held fixed, then the economy of an oil-dependent country will be considerably stable for higher investability, even in the stock market. However, since the determinants of the international crude oil price are enormous, it is difficult to fix it. This work focuses on investigating and modelling the nexus between crude oil price, Nigerian stock market indicators and the economic growth with cointegration and vector autoregressive (VAR) models.

1.2 Statement of Research Problem

One of the major factors that affect the prospects of an oil dependent economy is the crude oil price in the international market. Since the first oil price shock of 1974, the shocks have kept reoccurring. Between 1995 and 2014 these distortions have been so obvious and as such caused uncertainties in the exchange rates, planning and execution of vital projects in the economy, inability to adhere to wise fiscal policies and consequently affecting the

prospects of the stock market negatively being that Nigeria has oil as her major source of revenue. Being both an exporter of crude oil and importer of refined petroleum products, Nigeria economy is highly susceptible to the distortions in the crude oil prices, in most cases, the budgeting have been made with reference to threshold price of crude oil in the international market, share prices have been adjusted to reflect the benchmark price of crude oil as well.

Although large proceeds are being realized from the domestic sales and export of petroleum products, its effects on the growth of the Nigeria economy as regards returns and productivity, redistribution of fund for investment, stability of the naira per dollar exchange rate, infrastructural development, poverty eradication and an improvement in the standard of living of the citizens is still questionable, hence there is an urgent need to investigate the relationship between crude oil price, economic growth and stock market in Nigeria. It is on this note that this study seeks to proffer a framework for predictability of the dynamic relationship that exist amongst these variables so that stakeholders and policy makers may be well guided on how to improve the economic wellbeing of the country.

1.3 Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following questions?

- i. What time series models do Crude Oil Price (in USD per barrel), Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate (in USD) follow?
- ii. Is there any long term relationship(s) between Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate?
- iii. What multivariate time series model is appropriate in modelling the relationship that exists between these time series variables?
- iv. What is the nature of the future observations in terms of forecasts of these series?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of this work:

- i. To fit separate univariate time series models to Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate.
- ii. To investigate a long term relationship between the oil price, the indicators of the Nigerian Stock Market and the economic growth.
- iii. To fit a multivariate time series model to Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate.
- iv. Using the fitted univariate models and VAR model to forecast the Oil Prices, the Market Capitalization and the Exchange Rate.

1.5 Significance of the Study

- i. Empirically, this work will contribute to the existing literatures in this subject area, serving as a source of reference for further research work in this field of study.
- ii. Investigating the relationships between the crude oil prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate, will help in under-covering what helps in obtaining better the forecasts for these variables.
- iii. Modelling and forecasting these variables will present a framework that will help the government, stock brokers and policy makers to strategize better ways to improve the economy, trade their stock brokerages and formulate better polices, respectively.

1.6 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The coverage of this work is the monthly data of Crude Oil Prices (in USD per barrel), Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate (in USD) obtained from US Energy Information and Administration (EIA), the Nigeria Stock Exchange and Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, respectively, from January 1995 to November 2014. So, inferences made are within the confines of the data, its sources and duration. Exchange Rate (still a very salient indicator

of economic growth) is chosen as a proxy for economic growth instead of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) which is a more popular indicator because of unavailability of monthly data for the GDP. Market Capitalization is used as a proxy for stock market indicators.

1.7 Definition of Key Concepts

Stationarity: This is a term used in mathematics and statistics to refer to a stochastic process whose joint probability distribution does not change when shifted in time.

$$\text{That is, } F_{X(t_1), X(t_2), \dots, X(t_n)} = F_{X(t_1+k), X(t_2+k), \dots, X(t_n+k)},$$

for (t_1, \dots, t_n) and k integers. Where t_1, \dots, t_n are time and k is a time lag and F is an n -dimensional distribution function.

Cointegration: This is defined as a long run or equilibrium relationship between two or more non-stationary time series variables.

Vector Autoregression (VAR): This refers to statistical model used in capturing the interdependencies that exist among many time series variables.

Multivariate Time Series Analysis: This refers to the analysis used when one wants to model and explain the interaction and co-movements among a group of time series variables.

Market Capitalization: This is defined as product of the share price and the number of outstanding shares. Exchange rate is a very salient indicator of the economic growth.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Crude Oil Price, Stock Market and Economic Growth Relationship

The relation between crude oil price, stock market and the economic growth is a topic that has given birth to divergent views and opinions by different authors. Crude oil price being one of the major determinants of how well an oil dependent economy performs, has made many researchers to have interest in studying its effect on the economic variables. Depending on the economic variable, the shocks crude oil price exerts could be short-run and at times long-run and it could be positive or negative (Adaramola⁴, 2012). As asserted by Adebisi, Adenuga, Abeng and Omanukwue⁸ (2010), the oil crisis of the 1970s has made the literature to be gorged with oil prices explaining macroeconomic activities, irrespective of whether they are oil resource economies or not. Literatures have identified three measures of oil price. These are: the linear measure of oil price, asymmetric oil price measure and the net oil price increase. The linear or symmetric measure of oil price assumes that effects of oil price movements (increases or decreases) are equal such that a rise in oil price is expected to have a negative impact on the level of economic activity and oil price declines have a positive impact (Afshar, Arabian and Zomorrodian⁹, 2008). This explains the direct proportional relationship between oil price increase and the increase in the production cost of modernized economies that because of their expanded production objectives, their demand for oil increases. Net oil price increase has been identified as the quality by which oil prices exceeds its maximum value over the previous periods. Thus, if the current price of oil is higher than the maximum oil price of previous periods, then the percentage change between the two is computed. This measure of oil price assumes that when oil price is merely increasing to attain its maximum level in the previous period, it would have no impact (Adebisi⁸ *et al.*, 2010). However, when the current price of oil has increased to a level above its maximum value in the previous

periods, it is expected to have an impact (Hamilton and Lin¹⁰, 1998). Asymmetric oil price shocks refer to an oil price measure that differentiates between the positive and negative oil price volatility. In other words, a variable represents a positive percentage changes in oil price and another variable represents the negative percentage change (Mark¹¹, 1989, Lee and Ratti¹² 1995).

Another approach as asserted by Kilian¹³ (2009) is that conventional approach in the oil literature which treats oil price as exogenous variable with respect to the global economy should be done with. As argued by existing literatures (Barsky and Kilian¹⁴, 2004; Kilian¹⁵, 2008; Hamilton¹⁶, 2008), the same economic shocks that drives macroeconomic aggregate (which by extension implies stock prices) may likewise drive the oil prices, making it impossible to separate reverse causality. Therefore, it implies that aggregate oil price shocks must be decomposed into structural factors to reflect the endogenous character of such shocks. By way of using recursive structure, Kilian¹³ (2009) pointed to three oil shocks: an oil market specific shock, an oil supply shocks and a global demand shocks.

Following the above assertions, investigations on the relationship between the oil price shocks, stock prices and economic growth in both oil-exporting and oil-importing countries have yielded divergent results.

2.2 Relationship between Crude Oil Price and Stock Market Indicators

Jones and Kaul¹⁷ (1996) studied the response of international stock markets to changes in the oil price using quarterly data. The study aimed at stock returns from the US, Canada, the UK and Japan. They engaged simple regression models, and reported that the stock returns for all countries (except the UK) were negatively impacted by oil prices.

Sadorsky¹⁸ (1999) used monthly data to investigate the relationship between oil prices and stock returns for the US from 1947 to 1996:4. Making use of variance decomposition, the findings from this author suggested that oil prices and stock returns have a negative relationship in the short term, meaning that higher oil prices lead to lower stock returns.

In more recent studies, Anoruo and Mustapha¹⁹ (2007) investigated the relationship between oil and stock returns for the US using daily data, Johansen bi-variate co-integration and error correction approach. The results from this indicated long-run relationship between oil and stock returns in the US. The authors further opined that the estimated vector error correction model (VECM) provided evidence of causality from stock market returns to oil market returns and not vice versa. The authors stated that since the Johansen and Juselius estimation technique did not show evidence of co-integration but rather, the Gregory-Hansen co-integration provided co-integration in oil and stock markets, it therefore implies that both markets are integrated but not segmented.

Narayan and Narayan²⁰ (2010) assessed the relationship between oil prices and Vietnam's stock prices with daily series from 2000 to 2008. Using Johansen test, the findings provided evidence of oil prices, stock-prices, and exchange rates for Vietnam sharing a long-run relationship.

Adopting the approach by Kilian¹³ (2009) and Kilian and Park²¹ (2009) probed the impact of oil price shocks on US stock prices. The authors found out that oil demand shocks depress stock prices due to precautionary demand, where as oil price shocks driven by global economic expansion has a positive effect on stock prices and oil supply shocks had less impact on stock prices.

Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates; six members of the Gulf Co-operation Council (GCC), are symbols of promising, oil dependent emerging markets. The oil prices in this region taking its cue from the future prices of West Texas Intermediate (WTI), a primary crude oil stream traded on the New York Mercantile Exchange (NYMEX). Empirical evidence showed that there is a linkage between oil price volatility and the GCC stock market returns. Thus, oil price movement is an important barometer for investors to make necessary investment decisions and for policy makers to adopt appropriate policies in managing stock markets (Adebiyi⁸ *et al.*, 2010).

In a similar study conducted by Hammoudeh and Aleisa²² (2004), Johansen co-integration technique was employed to investigate the relationship between oil prices and stock markets in GCC countries. Conclusion reached was that Saudi market is the only market in the group that could be predicted by oil future prices. Similar study carried out by Arouri, Lahiani, and Bellalah²³ (2010) on GCC countries, the result showed that stock market returns significantly react to oil price changes in Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and United Arab Emirate (UAE). Results from the same study also showed that the oil price shocks do not affect stock market returns in Bahrain and Kuwait. These authors also established that the relationship between oil prices and stock markets in these countries are non-linear and switching according to oil prices. This implies that a particular direction of relationship between oil shocks and stock returns could not be identified since they are changing per regime.

Driespronga, Jacobsenb and Maat²⁴ (2003) findings suggest that oil price changes significantly predict negative excess returns and they also maintain that financial investors seem to under-react to information in the oil price. These authors observed a strong linkage between monthly stock returns and lagged monthly changes in oil price.

Cheung and Ng²⁵ (1998) employed the Johansen co-integration technique and established the existence of long-run co-movement between five national stock market indices and real oil price, real consumption, real money and real output. The author found that oil prices were negatively correlated with stock prices. Miller and Ratti²⁶ (2009) examined long-run relationship between the world crude oil price and international stock markets for the samples period 1971: 1-2008:3 using a co-integrated VECM. Concluded made was that international stock market indices respond negatively to increases in the oil price in the long run. The authors also established the existence of a long run co-movement between crude oil price and stock market during 1971:1 – 1980: 5 and 1988: 2- 1999:9 with evidence of break down in the relationship after the period. The authors submitted that it was suggestive of the

possibility that the relationship between real oil price and stock prices have changed in recent period compared to the earlier period.

Papapetrou²⁷ (2001) in an attempt to investigate the relationships among oil prices, real stock price, interest rates, real economic activity and employment for Greece used a multivariate vector-auto-regression (VAR) approach. The results found that while oil prices were important in explaining stock price movements, stock market returns did not lead to changes in real activity and employment. The authors, however, observed that changes in the oil price affected real economic activity and employment.

Park and Ratti²⁸ (2007) using multivariate VAR approach for a sample period 1986:1-2005:12 in Norway, an oil exporting economy like Nigeria, found out that oil price volatility accounted for six percent volatility in real stock returns. Bjornland²⁹ (2008) conducted similar study for the same country. In this case stock returns were incorporated in a structural VAR model, it was discovered that 10 percent rise in oil prices increase stock returns by 2.5 percent with robust results for linear and non-linear measures of oil prices. The author further concluded that the Norwegian economy responds to higher oil prices by increasing aggregate wealth and demand, while emphasizing the role of monetary policy shocks, in particular, as driving force behind stock price variability in the short run.

Eryigit³⁰ (2009) analyzed the impacts of oil price changes on the sectoral indices of the Turkish stock exchange using daily data sets. Using the ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique, he estimated an extended market model which included market return (in Turkish Lira, TL), oil price (in dollars, USD) and exchange rates (USD/TL) to determine the effects of oil price (USD) changes on market indices in Istanbul Stock Exchange (ISE) for the period of 2000-2008. It was discovered by this author that changes in oil price (TL) had significant effects on electricity, wholesale and retail trade, insurance, holding investment, wood, paper-printing, basic metal, metal and non-metal product, machinery and mineral products indices at the 5 percent significance level. In addition, changes in oil price (USD) had a significant positive effect on wood, paper printing, insurance, and electricity sub sector indices.

In a study by Cong, Wei, Jiao and Fan³¹ (2008), using a multivariate vector-autoregression (VAR), oil price shocks depress the stock prices of some Chinese oil companies. These authors observed that oil price shocks do have statistically significant effects only on manufacturing index and some oil companies. The oil price volatility increased the stock returns of manufacturing, mining, and petrochemical companies because of speculative activities arising from volatility in the oil prices, with less impact on the real stock returns of the Chinese stock market indices.

Using similar method of vector-autoregressive (VAR) but on different variables, Henriques and Sadorsky³² (2008) estimated the relationship between alternative energy stock prices and interest rates. These authors found that the technological stock prices and oil prices Granger-causes alternative energy companies' stock prices.

A study by Aspergis and Miller³³ (2009) using Kilian¹³ (2009) approach but with a bit modification employed a VAR analysis to investigate the effect of structural oil market shocks on stock prices in a multi-country context. In this study, it was found that oil-market shocks have a minor impact on international stock markets.

Basher, Haugh and Sadorsky³⁴ (2012) also employed a structural vector autoregressive (SVAR) approach to model the dynamics between real oil prices, exchange rates indices for major currencies, emerging market stock prices, interest rates, global real economic activity and oil supply. The result showed that the magnitude, direction and duration depends on whether the country is a net importer or exporter in the world oil market and whether changes in oil price are driven by supply or aggregate demand.

Lippi and Nobili³⁵ (2008) asserts that the source of oil shocks may affect economic performance differently; oil price increases due to higher oil demand shocks affect output differently than oil price increases due to lower world oil supply shocks. These authors argued that positive oil supply shocks decrease domestic production. In order to assess the effects of oil supply shocks, the authors employed the sign –restrictions approach pioneered by Canova and Nicolo³⁶ (2002) and Uhliq³⁷ (2005). A three variable VAR model was set that includes

world crude oil production, twelve real price changes, and domestic growth rates. The authors defined positive oil supply price shocks such that oil production decreases but oil prices increases at the contemporaneous period where no additional restrictions are put on for additional periods as well as for their effect on output.

As asserted by Guo and Kliesen³⁸ (2005), oil price shocks raise uncertainty about future oil prices and then delays in business investment (stock market investment inclusive).

In a research work by Fang, Noe and Tice³⁹ (2009) on the relationship between oil price shock and Chinese stock market. These authors used monthly data from 1997:7 to 2008:9 using VAR. They found out that only global supply shocks had a significant positive effect on China's stock returns, while global demand shocks and oil price related shocks had no significant impact on the China's stock returns. The insignificance of these shocks were explained by the fact that the positive expected effect on China's fast economic growth may almost be decayed by negative precautionary demand driven effect.

Now with particular reference given to Nigeria, many works have been done and literatures scripted around oil price shocks and macroeconomic variables but few of them are directed towards investigating connections between oil price shocks, stock market indices and economic growth.

Adaramola⁴ (2012) using monthly data spanning from 1985: 1 to 2009: 4 of crude oil price and All Share Price index (ASPI, a proxy for stock market indices) investigated the link of oil prices with stock prices behavior in Nigeria. The findings from this author using Johansen co-integration technique, error correction mechanism and Granger-causality test, revealed that oil prices exert significant shock on stock prices both in the short and long run. The author further maintained that there is a unidirectional causal relationship from oil price to stock returns.

Asaolu and Ilo⁵ (2012) utilized vector error correction model (VECM) to the oil price and stock market relationship and found that oil price shocks lead to a fall in stock market returns. Using a structural VAR model, Effiong⁴⁰ (2014) investigated the oil price shocks and

stock market relationship for Nigeria taking into account the origin of oil prices. The impact of the three sources of oil price shock on stock market were disentangled with the structural VAR framework and their interactions were analyzed based on impulse response functions and forecasting variance decomposition. This approach by Effiong⁴⁰ (2014) is based on Killian and Park²¹ (2009) framework. The author maintained that there is a shock exerted by oil price changes on stock market.

Using a structural VAR model, Mordi and Adebisi⁴¹ (2010) investigated the asymmetric effect of oil price shocks on output and prices in Nigeria. The authors maintained that positive oil price shocks are associated with an increase in real GDP after two months, whereas decrease in oil price significantly reduces real output immediately. In addition, the impact of oil price shock on money supply and all share price index (ASPI) is asymmetric; it raises the all share price index and money supply immediately.

A regime-based Granger Causality was employed by Ekong, Ezepe, Akpan and Moffat⁴² (2015) to assess the causal relationship that exists between the crude oil prices and the indicators of the stock market during the period of global financial crisis and the period of no global financial crisis. With the aid of dummy-augmented causality model, it was seen that there was a causal relationship between these variables in the two regimes. The authors also discovered that it is more ideal to analyze the causal relationship among these variables based on the two regimes.

2.3 Relationship between Crude Oil Price and Economic Growth

A study conducted in Turkey, an oil importing economy but rich in industrial base, by Ozturk, Feridun and Kalyoncu⁴³ (2008) using Johansen co-integration and Granger causality test on data from December, 1982- May, 2006 revealed that changes in the real international price of crude oil Granger causes fluctuations in real exchange rates.

In Singapore, a research carried out by Chang and Wong⁴⁴ (2003) to examine the effects of oil price shocks on the Singaporean economy revealed that there is an insignificant

negative relationship between the oil price shocks and the Singaporean gross domestic output, inflation rate and unemployment rate. On the contrary, the work by Farzanegan and Markwardt⁴⁵ (2009) on the Iranian economy projects a strong positive relationship between oil price distortions and industrial output growth.

Korhonen and Juurikkala⁴⁶ (2009), using pooled data from 1975-2005, showed that high oil price leads to appreciation of real exchange rate with the elasticity of exchange rate to oil price between 0.4 and 0.5. Examining the Algerian economy for the period 1970 to 2003, Koranchelian⁴⁷ (2005) adopted a VECM approach and concluded that movements in the real exchange rate were time varying and were accounted for by fluctuations in productivity and real oil prices with deviations from real exchange rate adjusting itself within nine months. In specific terms, the author found that a one percent rise in oil price led to an appreciation of real exchange rate by 0.2 percent.

Rasche and Tatom⁴⁸ (1977) argued that oil price fluctuations can be an important indicator of a supply-side shock that reduces the potential output of an economy. Thus, a rise in the price of crude oil indicates an increase in the scarcity of energy.

Nigeria economy being a net exporter of crude oil responds positively to the crude oil price distortions. Using VAR model, Umar and Abdulhakeem⁴⁹ (2010) conducted a study on oil price shocks and the Nigeria economy, the result showed a positive relationship between oil prices and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), inverse relationship between oil prices and unemployment and insignificant relation between oil prices and the Consumer Price Index (CPI).

Adebiyi *et al*⁸ (2010) studied the effects oil price shocks, exchange rates and stock market behavior of Nigeria using a multivariate VAR and Granger causality analysis. The authors were of the opinion that oil price shocks had an immediate and significant negative effect on real stock returns and the causation runs from oil price shocks to stock returns. Using Johansen Cointegration Test, it was observed that there is no long run relationship between interest rates, oil price, stock price and industrial production.

Studies by Olomola and Adejumo⁵⁰ (2006), Akpan⁵¹ (2009) and Oriakhi and Osaze⁵² (2013) have identified a positive relationship between oil price increase and growth of output in Nigeria.

Similar research works by Olusegun⁵³ (2008) and Philip and Akintoye⁵⁴ (2006) did not find any significant impact of oil price shock on variables like: money supply, price level, output and government expenditure.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Source of Data

The source of data for this research work is with particular reference to world crude oil prices, the indicators of economic growth and the indicators of the stock market in Nigeria.

3.2 Population and Sample Size

Monthly data for the crude oil prices, market capitalization and exchange rate were obtained for a period spanning from January 1995 to November 2014. Each of these series consists of 239 observations.

3.3 Instrument for Data Collection

Monthly data for the crude oil prices was obtained via www.eia.gov/dnas/pet-pet_pri_spt_sl_d.htm. Monthly data for Market Capitalization was purchased from the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), Stock Exchange House, 2-4 Customs Street, Lagos, Nigeria via contactcentre@nigerianstockexchange.com & www.nse.com.org. Data on Exchange Rate was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical database, www.cenbank.org.

3.4 Methods of Analysis

3.4.1 Software used in the Analysis

The analyses of these data sets were carried out by the use of the following statistical software; Eviews 7, Gretl, 1.9.5 and JMulTi 4. Eviews 7 was used to analyze lag structure, cointegration analysis and augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test. The Eviews outputs on the above analyses are very detailed and easy to understand and interpret. Gretl 1.9.5 was used to model the respective series as univariates, plotting of correlograms, performing Portmanteau test, correlation analysis and forecasting. Gretl 1.9.5 was chosen here since it uses a state space algorithm (Kalman Filter) in the estimation and this makes possible to fit models even at specific lags. By fitting models at specific lags, we mean jumping some lags and fitting the

models with desired and appropriate lags. JMulTi 4 was used to model the series as vector autoregressive (VAR), Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test, impose some restrictions on insignificant subsets for the VAR parameter estimation, forecasting and also used to perform both instantaneous and Granger-causality tests. Subset restrictions for VAR parameters cannot be easily achieved (if at all it is possible) with the earlier mentioned packages.

3.4.2 Stochastic Processes

A stochastic process is a family of random variables $\{X(t_i): i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ where $t_i \in \Lambda$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. An alternative way of describing a stochastic process is to give a formula for value $X(t)$ of the process at each point $t \in \Lambda$ in terms of a family of random variables whose probability law is known (Ebong⁵⁵, 1998).

3.4.3 Stationarity

A stochastic process whose common distribution function does not change when shifted in time is said to be stationary (Kirchgassner and Wolters⁵⁶, 2007).

Consider a finite set of random variables $\{X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, \dots, X_{t_n}\}$ from a stochastic process $\{X(\omega, t): t = 0, +1, +2, \dots\}$. Where ω belongs to the sample space and t belongs to an indexed set. The n-dimensional distribution function is defined as

$$F_{X_{t_1} \dots X_{t_n}}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = P\{\omega: X_{t_1} \leq x_1, X_{t_2} \leq x_2, \dots, X_{t_n} \leq x_n\} \quad (3.0)$$

where $x_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are any real numbers.

A process is said to be;

1. first-order stationary in distribution if its one-dimensional distribution is time invariant.

That is, if

$$F_{X_{t_1}}(x_1) = F_{X_{t_1+k}}(x_1) \quad (3.1)$$

for any t_1, k and $t_1 + k$.

2. second-order stationary in distribution if

$$F_{X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}}(x_1, x_2) = F_{X_{t_1+k}, X_{t_2+k}}(x_1, x_2) \quad (3.2)$$

for any set of $t_1, t_2, k, t_1 + k$ and $t_2 + k$.

3. the n th-order stationary in distribution if

$$F_{X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, \dots, X_{t_n}}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = F_{X_{t_1+k}, X_{t_2+k}, \dots, X_{t_n+k}}(x_1, x_2) \quad (3.3)$$

for (t_1, \dots, t_n) and k integers. Where t_1, \dots, t_n are time and k is a time lag.

A process is said to be strictly stationary if (3.3) is true for any n , i.e. $n = 1, 2, \dots$

A process $\{X_t\}$ is weakly stationary if the mean $E(X_t) = \mu$ is a fixed constant for all t and the autocovariances $Cov(X_t, X_{t+k}) = \gamma_k$ depend only on the time difference or time lag k for all t (Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁵⁷, 2008).

The term stationary in a wide sense or covariance stationary is also used to describe a second-order stationary process.

3.4.4 Autocovariance and Autocorrelation Functions

According to Wei⁵⁸ (2006), covariance between X_t and X_{t+k} denoted by $cov(X_t, X_{t+k})$ which is a function of the time difference k is called the autocovariance function $\{\gamma_k\}$ of the stochastic process. As function of k , γ_k is called the autocovariance function in the time series analysis since it represents the covariance between X_t and X_{t+k} from the same process.

It is defined as

$$\gamma_k = cov(X_t, X_{t+k}) = E[(X_t - \mu)(X_{t+k} - \mu)] \quad (3.4)$$

The sample estimate of γ_k is C_k given by

$$C_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^{n-k} (X_t - \bar{X})(X_{t+k} - \bar{X}) \quad (3.5)$$

Similarly, correlation between X_t and X_{t+k} denoted by $corr(X_t, X_{t+k})$ which is a function of the time difference k is called the autocorrelation function $\{\rho_k\}$ of the stochastic process. As function of k , ρ_k is called the autocorrelation function in the time series analysis since it represents the correlation between X_t and X_{t+k} from the same process. It is defined as

$$\rho_k = \frac{cov(X_t, X_{t+k})}{\sqrt{var(X_t)}\sqrt{var(X_{t+k})}} = \frac{\gamma_k}{\gamma_0} \quad (3.6)$$

The corresponding sample estimate is given by

$$\hat{\rho}_k = \frac{c_k}{c_0}, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (3.7)$$

where

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (X_t - \bar{X})^2 \quad (3.8)$$

Bartlett⁵⁹ (1946) has shown that for a stationary Gaussian process,

$$Cov(\hat{\rho}_k, \hat{\rho}_{k+j}) \approx \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} (\rho_i \rho_{i+j} + \rho_{i+k+j} \rho_{i-k} - 2\rho_k \rho_i \rho_{i-j-k} - 2\rho_{k+j} \rho_i \rho_{i-k} + 2\rho_k \rho_{k+j} \rho_i^2) \quad (3.9)$$

for $k > 0$ and $k + j > 0$

For large n , $\hat{\rho}_k$ is approximately normally distributed with mean μ and variance

$$Var(\hat{\rho}_k) \approx \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} (\rho_i^2 + \rho_{i+k} \rho_{i-k} - 4\rho_k \rho_i \rho_{i-k} + 2\rho_k^2 \rho_i^2) \quad (3.10)$$

For the process in which $\rho_k = 0$ for $k > m$, Bartlett's approximation of (3.10) becomes

$$Var(\hat{\rho}_k) \approx \frac{1}{n} (1 + 2\rho_1^2 + 2\rho_2^2 + \dots + \rho_m^2) \quad (3.11)$$

Practically, $\rho_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ are unknown and are replaced by their sample estimates, $\hat{\rho}_i$, and

$$S_{\hat{\rho}_k} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} (1 + 2\hat{\rho}_1^2 + 2\hat{\rho}_2^2 + \dots + \hat{\rho}_m^2)} \quad (3.12)$$

is the associated large lag standard error of $\hat{\rho}_k$ (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

3.4.5 Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF)

The conditional correlation between X_t and X_{t+k} after their mutual linear dependency on the intervening variables $X_{t+1}, X_{t+2}, \dots, X_{t+k-1}$ has been removed given by $Corr(X_t, X_{t+k} | X_{t+1}, X_{t+2}, \dots, X_{t+k-1})$ is usually referred to as the partial autocorrelation in time series analysis (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

Partial autocorrelation can be derived from the regression model, where the dependent variable X_{t+k} from a zero mean stationary process is regressed on k lagged variables $X_{t+k-1}, X_{t+k-2}, \dots$ and X_t , i.e.

$$X_{t+k} = \phi_{k1} X_{t+k-1} + \phi_{k2} X_{t+k-2} + \dots + \phi_{kk} X_t + \alpha_{t+k} \quad (3.13)$$

where ϕ_{ki} denotes the i th regression parameter and α_{t+k} is an error term with mean zero and uncorrelated with X_{t+k-j} for $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Multiplying X_{t+k-j} on both sides of the above regression equation in (3.13) and taking the expectation, we get

$$\gamma_j = \phi_{k1}\gamma_{j-1} + \phi_{k2}\gamma_{j-2} + \dots + \phi_{kk}\gamma_{j-k} \quad (3.14)$$

Hence,

$$\rho_j = \phi_{k1}\rho_{j-1} + \phi_{k2}\rho_{j-2} + \dots + \phi_{kk}\rho_{j-k} \quad (3.15)$$

For $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$, we have the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 &= \phi_{k1}\rho_0 + \phi_{k2}\rho_1 + \dots + \phi_{kk}\rho_{k-1} \\ \rho_2 &= \phi_{k1}\rho_1 + \phi_{k2}\rho_2 + \dots + \phi_{kk}\rho_{k-1} \\ &\vdots \\ \rho_k &= \phi_{k1}\rho_{k-1} + \phi_{k2}\rho_{k-2} + \dots + \phi_{kk}\rho_0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

which can be written in a matrix form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 & \rho_2 & \dots & \rho_{k-1} \\ \rho_1 & 1 & \rho_1 & \dots & \rho_{k-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{k-1} & \rho_{k-2} & \rho_{k-3} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{k1} \\ \phi_{k2} \\ \vdots \\ \phi_{kk} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_1 \\ \rho_2 \\ \vdots \\ \rho_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.17)$$

Using Cramer's rule successively for $k = 1, 2, \dots$, we have

$$\text{For } k = 1, j = 1; \quad \rho_1 = \phi_{11}$$

$$\text{For } k = 2, j = 1, 2; \quad \rho_j = \phi_{21}\rho_{j-1} + \phi_{22}\rho_{j-2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho_1 = \phi_{21} + \phi_{22}\rho_1$$

$$\rho_2 = \phi_{21}\rho_1 + \phi_{22}$$

$$\phi_{22} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 \\ \rho_1 & \rho_2 \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 \\ \rho_1 & 1 \end{vmatrix}}$$

$$\text{For } k = 3, j = 1, 2, 3; \quad \rho_j = \phi_{31}\rho_{j-1} + \phi_{32}\rho_{j-2} + \phi_{33}\rho_{j-3}$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho_1 = \phi_{31} + \phi_{32}\rho_1 + \phi_{33}\rho_2$$

$$\rho_2 = \phi_{31}\rho_1 + \phi_{32} + \phi_{33}\rho_1$$

$$\rho_3 = \phi_{31}\rho_2 + \phi_{32}\rho_1 + \phi_{33}$$

$$\Phi_{33} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 & \rho_1 \\ \rho_1 & 1 & \rho_2 \\ \rho_2 & \rho_1 & \rho_3 \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 & \rho_2 \\ \rho_1 & 1 & \rho_1 \\ \rho_2 & \rho_1 & 1 \end{vmatrix}}$$

And in general,

$$\Phi_{kk} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 & \rho_2 & \dots & \rho_{k-2} & \rho_1 \\ \rho_1 & 1 & \rho_1 & \dots & \rho_{k-3} & \rho_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \rho_{k-1} & \rho_{k-2} & \rho_{k-3} & \dots & \rho_1 & \rho_k \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_1 & \rho_2 & \dots & \rho_{k-2} & \rho_{k-1} \\ \rho_1 & 1 & \rho_1 & \dots & \rho_{k-3} & \rho_{k-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \rho_{k-1} & \rho_{k-2} & \rho_{k-3} & \dots & \rho_1 & 1 \end{vmatrix}}$$

Notice for Φ_{kk} , the determinant in the numerator has the same elements as that in the denominator, but the last column is replaced by $(\rho_1, \dots, \rho_k)'$. The quantity Φ_{kk} , regarded as a function of lag k , is called the partial autocorrelation function (Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁵⁷, 2008). Thus, the autocorrelation between X_t and X_{t+k} can be obtained as the regression coefficient associated with X_t when regressing X_{t+k} on its k lagged variables $X_{t+k-1}, X_{t+k-2}, \dots$ and X_t .

3.4.6 Sample Partial Autocorrelation Function

A recursive method starting with $\hat{\rho}_1 = \hat{\Phi}_{11}$ for the computation of the sample PACF, $\hat{\Phi}_{kk}$ has been given by Durbin⁶⁰ (1960) as follows:

$$\hat{\Phi}_{k+1,k+1} = \frac{\hat{\rho}_{k+1} - \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{\Phi}_{kj} \hat{\rho}_{k+1-j}}{1 - \sum_{j=1}^k \hat{\Phi}_{kj} \hat{\rho}_j} \quad (3.18)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{\Phi}_{k+1,j} = \hat{\Phi}_{k,j} - \hat{\Phi}_{k+1,k+1} \hat{\Phi}_{k,k+1-j}, j = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (3.19)$$

On the hypothesis that the underlying process is a white noise, the variance of $\hat{\Phi}_{kk}$ can be approximated by

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\Phi}_{kk}) \approx \frac{1}{n} \quad (3.20)$$

Hence, $\pm \frac{2}{\sqrt{n}}$ can be used as approximate 95% critical limits on Φ_{kk} to test the hypothesis of a white noise process.

3.4.7 Unit Root Tests

As a prerequisite for any further analysis in time series modelling, it is pertinent to formally diagnose the characteristics of the series that are used in the study. This process is a complementary procedure to investigate the stationarity of the variables and also ascertain the order of integration of the variables. A nonstationary series is said to be integrated of order d , denoted $I(d)$, if it becomes stationary after being differenced d times (Greene⁶¹, 2012). Here, the order of integration means the number of times each of the series will be differenced before stationarity is attained. With the result from the unit root test, the ACF and the PACF, proper investigation into the nature of the variables in terms of stationarity will be made. Augmented Dickey-Fuller⁶² (1979) test shall be used to achieve this unit root test.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is based on the regression equation,

$$y_t = \phi y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \gamma_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t$$

which can also be written as,

$$\Delta y_t = \beta y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \gamma_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.21)$$

Where y_t is the series being tested and p is the number of lagged differenced terms included to capture any autocorrelation, $\beta = \phi - 1$, $\Delta y_{t-j} = (y_{t-j} - y_{t-j-1})$.

The null hypothesis is that the series contains a unit root.

$$H_0: \beta = 0$$

against

$$H_1: \beta < 0$$

$$\text{Test statistic: } T = \frac{\hat{\beta}}{S.E.(\hat{\beta})} \equiv \frac{\hat{\phi}-1}{S.E.(\hat{\phi})} \sim t_{\alpha}(n) \text{ at } \alpha \text{ level of significance}$$

If the null hypothesis is rejected, we conclude that the series contains a unit root. This implies, however, only that the series y_t is integrated of order $d \geq 1$. To find out the order of required differencing, the above test repeated on the series Δy_t , $\Delta^2 y_t$, and so on until an order of integration is reached. A nonstationary series may not be homogeneous and no differencing of any order may transform it into a stationary series. In such case, some other transformation

procedures may be necessary. In practice, however, for most homogenous nonstationary series the required order of differencing is rarely greater than 2 (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

It is worthy of note that the major problem with the ADF unit root test is that it has low power. The test is criticized on the ground that there is a decreased ability to reject a null hypothesis of unit root when it is actually false. To make the argument more specific, testing for unit root with ADF may make false conclusion that there is a unit root even when there is none (Theodoridis and Kader⁶³, 2014).

3.4.8 Moving Average (MA) Process

According to Wei⁵⁸ (2006), a stochastic process $\{X_t\}$ is a moving average process of order q and is denoted by $MA(q)$ if

$$\dot{X}_t = \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.22)$$

where

$$\dot{X}_t = X_t - \mu$$

Using the backward shift operator, we have

$$\dot{X}_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t$$

where

- (i) $B^s \varepsilon_t = \varepsilon_{t-s}$ is a backward shift operator
- (ii) $\theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \dots - \theta_q B^q$
- (iii) $\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_q$ is a finite set of weighted parameters, where $\psi_i = -\theta_i, \forall = 1, 2, \dots, q$
- (iv) ε_t is a white noise process with mean, zero and variance σ^2

Because $1 + \theta_1^2 + \theta_2^2 + \dots + \theta_q^2 < \infty$, a finite moving average process is stationary.

Moving average process is invertible if the root of $\theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \dots - \theta_q B^q = 0$ lie outside of the unit circle. The moving average processes are useful in describing phenomena in which events produce an immediate effect that only lasts for short time periods.

For $MA(q)$ process,

$$\dot{X}_t = \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$$

$$\gamma_0 = E(\dot{X}_t)^2 = E(X_t - \mu)^2 = E(\varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q})^2$$

$$\gamma_0 = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \theta_1^2 \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \dots + \theta_q^2 \sigma_\varepsilon^2$$

$$\gamma_0 = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 (1 + \theta_1^2 + \dots + \theta_q^2)$$

The variance is

$$\gamma_0 = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 \sum_{j=0}^q \theta_j^2$$

where $\theta_0 = 1$ and $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 = E(\varepsilon_t^2)$

$$\gamma_k = E(X_t - \mu)(X_{t-k} - \mu), k = 1, 2, \dots, q$$

$$\gamma_k = E(\varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q})(\varepsilon_{t-k} - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-k-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-k-q})$$

$$\gamma_k = -\theta_k E[\varepsilon_{t-k}^2] + \theta_1 \theta_{k+1} E[\varepsilon_{t-k-1}^2] + \dots + \theta_{q-k} \theta_q E[\varepsilon_{t-q}^2]$$

$$\gamma_k = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 (-\theta_k + \theta_1 \theta_{k+1} + \dots + \theta_{q-k} \theta_q)$$

The autocovariances are

$$\gamma_k = \begin{cases} \sigma_\varepsilon^2 (-\theta_k + \theta_1 \theta_{k+1} + \dots + \theta_{q-k} \theta_q), & k = 1, 2, \dots, q \\ 0 & k > q \end{cases} \quad (3.23)$$

Hence, the autocorrelation function becomes

$$\rho_k = \begin{cases} \frac{-\theta_k + \theta_1 \theta_{k+1} + \dots + \theta_{q-k} \theta_q}{1 + \theta_1^2 + \dots + \theta_q^2}, & k = 1, 2, \dots, q \\ 0, & k > q \end{cases} \quad (3.24)$$

If $\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_q$ are known, the q equations (3.24) may be solved for the parameters

$\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_q$. By substituting estimates C_k for ρ_k in 3.24 and solving the resulting equations,

estimates of the moving average parameters, $\hat{\theta}_1, \hat{\theta}_2, \dots, \hat{\theta}_q$, may be obtained.

3.4.9 Invertibility Conditions for Moving Average Process

The invertibility conditions for $MA(q)$ process may be obtained by writing

$$\dot{X}_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \text{ as } \varepsilon_t = \theta^{-1}(B)\dot{X}_t.$$

Hence, if $\theta(B) = \prod_{i=1}^q (1 - \pi_i B)$

where $\pi_1^{-1}, \dots, \pi_q^{-1}$ are roots of $\theta(B) = 0$, then on expanding in partial fractions, we obtain

$$\theta^{-1}(B) = \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\frac{M_i}{1 - \pi_i B} \right)$$

$\Pi(B)$ converges if $|\pi_i| < 1$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, q$. It follows that the invertibility condition for an $MA(q)$ process is that the roots π_i^{-1} of the characteristic equation

$$\theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q = 0$$

lie outside the unit circle.

Since the series $\psi(B) = \theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q$ is finite, no restrictions are needed on the parameters of the moving average process to ensure stationarity.

3.4.10 Autoregressive (AR) Process

A stochastic process $\{X_t\}$ is an autoregressive process of order p and is denoted by $AR(p)$ (Wei⁵⁸, 2006), if

$$\dot{X}_t = \phi_1 \dot{X}_{t-1} + \phi_2 \dot{X}_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p \dot{X}_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.25)$$

where

$$\dot{X}_t = X_t - \mu$$

Using the backward shift operator, it is seen that

$$\theta(B)\dot{X}_t = \varepsilon_t$$

where

- (i) $B^s \dot{X}_t = \dot{X}_{t-s}$ is a backward shift operator
- (ii) $\theta(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_q B^q$
- (iii) $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_q$ is a finite set of weighted parameters
- (iv) ε_t is a white noise process with mean, zero and variance σ^2

Because $\sum_{j=1}^p |\phi_j| < \infty$, the process is always invertible. For autoregressive process to be stationary, the roots of $\theta(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_q B^q = 0$ must lie outside of the unit circle.

The roots of $\theta(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_q B^q = 0$ are the reciprocal of the root of the polynomial equation in m . The AR processes are useful in describing situations in which the present value of a time series depends on its preceding values plus a random shock. The

covariance function can be obtained by multiplying \dot{X}_{t-k} on both sides of (3.25) and taking expectations, then

$$\gamma_k = \phi_1 \gamma_{k-1} + \phi_2 \gamma_{k-2} + \dots + \phi_p \gamma_{k-p}, \quad k > 0 \quad (3.26)$$

$$\text{where } E(\dot{X}_{t-k} \varepsilon_t) = \begin{cases} \sigma_\varepsilon^2, & \text{for } k = 0 \\ 0, & \text{for } k > 0 \end{cases}$$

dividing (3.26) by γ_0 , we have the following recursive relationship for the autocorrelation

$$\rho_k = \phi_1 \rho_{k-1} + \phi_2 \rho_{k-2} + \dots + \phi_p \rho_{k-p}, \quad k > 0 \quad (3.27)$$

3.4.11 Stationarity Condition for Autoregressive (AR) Process

For the general AR process $\phi(B)\dot{X}_t = \varepsilon_t$, written as

$$\dot{X}_t = \phi^{-1}(B)\varepsilon_t \equiv \psi(B)\varepsilon_t = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \psi_j \varepsilon_{t-j}$$

provided that the RHS expression converges.

$$\text{We obtain } \phi(B) = (1 - \tau_1 B)(1 - \tau_2 B) \dots (1 - \tau_p B)$$

where $\tau_i^{-1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ are the roots of $\phi(B) = 0$ and expanding $\phi^{-1}(B)$ in partial fractions, it is seen that

$$\dot{X}_t = \phi^{-1}(B)\varepsilon_t = \sum_{i=1}^p \left(\frac{k_i}{1 - \tau_i B} \right) \varepsilon_t$$

Hence, if the series $\psi(B) = \phi^{-1}(B)$ converges for $|B| < 1$, then $|\tau_i| < 1$, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$. Equivalently, the roots of

$$\phi(B) = (1 - \tau_1 B)(1 - \tau_2 B) \dots (1 - \tau_p B) = 0$$

must lie outside of the unit circle. Since the series $\Pi(B) = \phi(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_p B^p$ is finite, no restrictions are required on the parameters of an autoregressive process to ensure invertibility (Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁵⁷, 2008).

3.4.12 Mixed Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) Process

A natural extension of pure autoregressive and pure moving average processes is the mixed autoregressive moving average (ARMA) processes, which includes the autoregressive and moving average as special cases (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

A stochastic process $\{X_t\}$ is an $ARMA(p, q)$ process if $\{X_t\}$ is stationary and if for every t ,

$$\phi(B)\dot{X}_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.28)$$

For uniqueness of representation, we require that $\phi(B)$ and $\theta(B)$ are relatively prime as polynomials in B . For the process to be invertible, it is required that the roots of $\theta(B) = 0$ lie outside the unit circle. And also, for the process to be stationary, it is required that the roots of $\phi(B) = 0$ lie outside the unit circle. The stationary and invertible ARMA process can be written in pure autoregressive representation, that is,

$$\Pi(B)\dot{X}_t = \varepsilon_t \quad (3.29)$$

$$\text{where } \Pi(B) = \frac{\phi(B)}{\theta(B)} = (1 - \Pi_1 B - \Pi_2 B^2 - \dots) \quad (3.30)$$

This process can also be written as pure moving average representation

$$\dot{X}_t = \psi(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.31)$$

$$\text{where } \psi(B) = \frac{\theta(B)}{\phi(B)} = (1 - \psi_1 B - \psi_2 B^2 - \dots)$$

to derive the autocorrelation function, then

$$\dot{X}_t = \phi_1 \dot{X}_{t-1} + \phi_2 \dot{X}_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p \dot{X}_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.32)$$

Multiplying (3.32) by \dot{X}_{t-k} and taking the expectation yields

$$\gamma_k = \phi_1 \gamma_{k-1} + \phi_2 \gamma_{k-2} + \dots + \phi_p \gamma_{k-p}, \quad k \geq q + 1 \quad (3.33)$$

where $E(\dot{X}_{t-k} \varepsilon_{t-i}) = 0$ for $k > i$

dividing (3.33) by γ_0 , results in the following recursive relationship for the autocorrelation

$$\rho_k = \phi_1 \rho_{k-1} + \phi_2 \rho_{k-2} + \dots + \phi_p \rho_{k-p}, \quad k \geq q + 1 \quad (3.34)$$

3.4.13 Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Model

Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁵⁷ (2008) consider the extension of ARMA model

(3.28) to deal with homogenous non-stationary time series in which X_t itself is non-stationary

but its d th difference is a stationary ARMA model. Denoting the d th difference of X_t by

$$Y_t = (1 - B)^d \dot{X}_t \quad (3.35)$$

It can be written that

$$\phi(B)Y_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.36)$$

The corresponding model of X_t is

$$\phi(B)(1 - B)^d \dot{X}_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.37)$$

$$\phi(B)\dot{X}_t = \phi(B)\nabla^d \dot{X}_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.38)$$

where $\phi(B)$ is a stationary autoregressive operator. Since $\nabla^d \dot{X}_t = \nabla^d X_t$ for $d \geq 1$, where $\nabla = 1 - B$ is the difference operator.

$$\phi(B)\nabla^d X_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.39)$$

(3.39) is called an autoregressive integrated moving average model and can be referred to as an *ARIMA*(p, d, q) model. Equivalently, the process is defined by the two equations

$$\phi(B)w_t = \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.40)$$

and

$$w_t = \nabla^d X_t \quad (3.41)$$

An alternative way of looking at the process for $d \geq 1$ results from inverting (3.41) to result

$$X_t = S^d w_t \quad (3.42)$$

where S is the summation operator defined by

$$\begin{aligned} Sx_t &= \sum_{h=-\infty}^t x_h = (1 + B + B^2 + \dots)x_t \\ &= (1 - B)^{-1}x_t = \nabla^{-1}x_t \end{aligned} \quad (3.43)$$

Thus, $S = (1 - B)^{-1} = \nabla^{-1}$

The operator S^2 is similarly defined as

$$\begin{aligned} S^2x_t &= Sx_t + Sx_{t-1} + Sx_{t-2} + \dots \\ &= \sum_{i=-\infty}^t \sum_{h=-\infty}^i x_h = (1 + 2B + 3B^2 + \dots)x_t \end{aligned} \quad (3.44)$$

and so on for higher-order d .

3.4.14 General Form of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model

A slight extension of the ARIMA model of (3.39) is obtained by adding a constant term θ_0 . Thus, a general form of the model used to describe time series is the autoregressive integrated moving average process

$$\varphi(B)X_t = \phi(B)\nabla^d X_t = \theta_0 + \theta(B)\varepsilon_t \quad (3.45)$$

where

$$\phi(B) = 1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_q B^q$$

and

$$\theta(B) = 1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q$$

Then,

$\phi(B)$ will be called the autoregressive operator and it is assumed to be stationary, that is, the roots of $\phi(B) = 0$ lie outside of the unit circle

$\varphi(B) = \phi(B)\nabla^d$ will be called the generalized autoregressive operator; it is nonstationary operator with d of the roots of $\varphi(B) = 0$ equal to unity. $\theta(B)$ will be called the moving average operator; it is assumed to be invertible, that is, the roots of $\theta(B) = 0$ lie outside the unit circle.

The parameter θ_0 plays very different roles for $d = 0$ and $d > 0$. When $d = 0$, the model (3.45) represents a stationary process, and θ_0 is related to the mean of the process, that is,

$$\theta_0 = \mu(1 - \phi_1 - \dots - \phi_p) \text{ (Wei}^{58}, 2006).$$

3.4.15 Univariate Time Series Modelling

Box and Jenkins three-stage iterative procedure is employed in modelling these series. The stages are as follows: identification, estimation and diagnostic checking.

3.4.16 Identification of Univariate Time Series Models

The traditional tools used in the identification of the model of a time series are the Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) and the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) of the said series. A series is modeled as an $AR(p)$ if the ACF tails off as a mixture of damped

exponential decays and/or the PACF cuts off after lag p . On the other hand, a series is modeled as $MA(q)$ if the PACF tails off as a mixture of exponential decays and/or damped sine waves depending on the nature of the roots of $\theta(B) = 0$ and the ACF cuts off after lag q . If both the ACF and PACF tail off, a mixed process is suggested (Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁵⁷, 2008). For an $AR(p)$ model, the ACF tails off as a mixture of damped exponential decays and/or damped sine wave and the PACF cuts off after lag p . In the same vein, for an $MA(q)$ model, the PACF tails off as a mixture of exponential decays and/or damped sine waves depending on the nature of the roots of $\theta(B) = 0$ and the ACF cuts off after lag. And for a mixed $ARMA(p, q)$ model, the ACF and PACF tail off.

3.4.17 Estimation of Parameters of the Models

Here consideration is given only to two methods of estimation of the parameters

$\phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_p)$, $\mu = E(X_t)$, $\theta = \theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_q$ and $\sigma_\varepsilon^2 = E(\varepsilon_t^2)$ from observations of the causal $ARMA(p, q)$ process defined by

$$\dot{X}_t = \phi_1 \dot{X}_{t-1} + \phi_2 \dot{X}_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p \dot{X}_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.46)$$

where $\varepsilon_t \sim WN(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$ and $\dot{X}_t = X_t - \mu$.

Where WN stands for White Noise.

(a.) Maximum Likelihood Method

Discussion shall centre on the two methods of maximum likelihood estimation generally considered in time series analysis.

(i) Conditional Maximum Likelihood Estimation

For $ARMA(p, q)$ model (3.46), the joint probability density function of

$\varepsilon = \{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_n\}'$ is given by

$$P(\varepsilon | \phi, \mu, \theta, \sigma_\varepsilon^2) = (2\pi\sigma_\varepsilon^2)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\sigma_\varepsilon^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i^2\right\} \quad (3.47)$$

Rewriting (3.47) as

$$\varepsilon_t = \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \dot{X}_t - \phi_1 \dot{X}_{t-1} - \phi_2 \dot{X}_{t-2} - \dots - \phi_p \dot{X}_{t-p} \quad (3.48)$$

Let $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)'$ and assume initial conditions $\mathbf{X}_* = (X_{1-p}, \dots, X_{-2}, X_{-1}, X_0)'$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_* = (\varepsilon_{1-p}, \dots, \varepsilon_{-2}, \varepsilon_{-1}, \varepsilon_0)'$ are known. The conditional log-likelihood function is

$$\ln L_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \sigma_\varepsilon^2) = -\frac{2}{n}(2\pi\sigma_\varepsilon^2) - \frac{S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta})}{2\sigma_\varepsilon^2} \quad (3.49)$$

$$\text{where } S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{t=1}^n \varepsilon_t^2(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{X}_*, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_*, \mathbf{X}) \quad (3.50)$$

is the conditional sum of squares function. The quantities $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ which maximize (3.49) are called the conditional estimators. Because $L_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta}, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$ involves the data only through $S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$, these estimators are the same as the conditional least squares estimators obtained from minimizing the conditional sum of squares function $S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$. The estimator $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2$ of σ_ε^2 is obtained from

$$\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2 = \frac{S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta})}{n-p-q-1} \quad (3.51)$$

where $n-p-q-1$ (degrees of freedom) equals the number of terms used in the sum of $S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$ minus the number of parameters' estimator.

(ii) Unconditional Maximum Likelihood Estimation

The method involves backcasting the unknown values $\mathbf{X}_* = (X_{1-p}, \dots, X_{-2}, X_{-1}, X_0)'$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_* = (\varepsilon_{1-p}, \dots, \varepsilon_{-2}, \varepsilon_{-1}, \varepsilon_0)'$ needed in the computation of the sum of squares and likelihood functions. This is possible because any ARMA model can be written in either the forward from

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_q B^q) \dot{X}_t = (1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q) \varepsilon_t \quad (3.52)$$

or the backward form

$$(1 - \phi_1 F - \dots - \phi_q F^q) \dot{X}_t = (1 - \theta_1 F - \theta_2 F^2 - \dots - \theta_q F^q) \varepsilon_t \quad (3.53)$$

where $F^s \dot{X}_t = \dot{X}_{t+i}$

the last two equations above should have the same autocorrelation structure because of stationarity. (3.52) can be used to forecast the unknown future values X_{n+j} for $j > 0$ based on the data (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n) and (3.53) can be used to forecast the unknown past values X_j and hence compute ε_j for $j \leq 0$ based on the data $(X_n, X_{n-1}, \dots, X_1)$.

Therefore, for further improvement in estimation, Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁶⁴ (1994) in Wei⁵⁸ (2006) suggest the following unconditional log-likelihood function:

$$\ln L_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta, \sigma_\varepsilon^2) = -\frac{2}{n}(2\pi\sigma_\varepsilon^2) - \frac{S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta)}{2\sigma_\varepsilon^2} \quad (3.54)$$

where

$$S(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta) = [E(\varepsilon_t | \boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta, \mathbf{X})]^2 \quad (3.55)$$

is the conditional sum of squares function.

where $E(\varepsilon_t | \boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta, \mathbf{X})$ is the conditional expectation of ε_t given $\boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta$, and \mathbf{X} (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

The quantities $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}, \hat{\mu}$, and $\hat{\theta}$ that minimize function (3.54) are called unconditional maximum likelihood estimators are equivalent to the unconditional least squares estimators obtained by minimizing (3.55). In practice, the summation in (3.55) is approximated by a finite form

$$S(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta) = \sum_{i=-M}^n [E(\varepsilon_t | \boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta, \mathbf{X})]^2 \quad (3.56)$$

where M is sufficiently large integer.

The estimator $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2$ of σ_ε^2 is obtained from

$$\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2 = \frac{S_*(\boldsymbol{\phi}, \mu, \theta)}{n} \quad (3.57)$$

(b.) Least Squares Method

Least squares approach is an estimating approach where one chooses the particular set of coefficients making the sum of squared errors ($\varepsilon' \varepsilon$) as small as possible. The application of least squares to models of the form

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \dots - \phi_q B^q)(1 - B)^d \dot{X}_t = (1 - \theta_1 B - \theta_2 B^2 - \dots - \theta_q B^q) \varepsilon_t \quad (3.58)$$

raises two problems

i. the equations will involve unknown “starting values

$Y_0, Y_{-1}, Y_{-2}, \dots, Y_{1-p}; \varepsilon_0, \varepsilon_{-1}, \varepsilon_{-2}, \dots, \varepsilon_{1-q}$.

ii. the model is in general, nonlinear in the coefficients to be estimated.

Two approaches to the starting value problem are possible. In the first approach, the unknown “starting values” are simply replaced by some appropriate assumed values and estimation is conditional on these assumed values. A more efficient unconditional approach is

based on estimating the starting values from the given sample data. The problem of nonlinearity can be overcome with the use of familiar nonlinear regression routines which are widely applicable in other fields (Granger and Newbold⁶⁵, 1977).

3.4.18 Diagnostic Checking of the Univariate Time Series Models

Diagnostic checking is applied with objective of uncovering possible lack of fit of the tentative model and possibly unravels the cause of such lack of fit. If no lack of fit is indicated, the model is ready to be used. In other words, if any inadequacy is found, the iterative cycle of identification, estimation and diagnostic checking is repeated until a suitable and appropriate representation is obtained.

Once the parameters of the tentative model have been estimated, checking whether or not the residuals obtained from the estimated equation are approximately white noise is carried out. This is done by examining the ACF and PACF of the residuals to see whether they are statistically insignificant, that is, within two standard deviations at 5% level of significance. If the residuals are approximately white noise, the model may be entertained provided the parameters are significantly different from zero.

Portmanteau Lack of Fit test uses the residual sample ACFs as a unit to check the joint null hypothesis

$$H_0: \rho_1 = \rho_2 = \dots = \rho_k = 0$$

where $\rho_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ are the autocorrelation of the residuals

with the test statistic

$$Q = n(n + 2) \sum_{j=1}^k (n - j)^{-1} \rho_j^2 \quad (3.59)$$

where n denotes the length of the series after any differencing. This test statistic is the modified Q statistic originally proposed by Box and Pierce⁶⁶ (1970). Under the null hypothesis of model adequacy, Ljung and Box⁶⁷ (1978), see Ansley and Newbold⁶⁸ (1979b), show that the Q statistic approximately follows $\chi_{\alpha, (k-m)}^2$ distribution, where $m = p + q$. Here p and q are respectively the orders of the Autoregressive and Moving Average components. This statistic is evaluated for several choices of k .

3.4.19 Multivariate Time Series

Many time series arising in practice are best considered as components of some vector-valued (multivariate) time series $\{X_t\}$ having not only serial dependence within each component series $\{X_{ti}\}$ and $\{X_{tj}\}$, $i \neq j$ (Brockwell and Davies⁶⁹, 2002).

For n -related time series variables of interest in a dynamic system $\mathbf{X} = (X_{1t}, X_{2t}, \dots, X_{nt})'$, methods of multivariate time series analysis are used to study the dynamic relationship among these variables. This involves the development of statistical models and methods of analysis that adequately describe the interrelationships among the series. Two main purposes for analyzing and modelling the vector of time series jointly are to gain an understanding of the dynamic relationships (both instantaneous and the long run) over time among the series and to improve the accuracy of forecasts for individual series by utilizing the additional information available from the related series in the forecast for each series (Box, Jenkins and Reinsel⁵⁷, 2008).

3.4.20 Cointegration Analysis

Cointegration is a statistical concept which unravels the existence of a long run equilibrium relationship among time series variables. It can be defined as a statistical process that yields a stationary series from a linear combination of two or more nonstationary series. The idea behind this is that, if two or more series are themselves nonstationary, but a linear combination of them is stationary, then the variables are said to be cointegrated (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

Cointegration is defined as a long run or equilibrium relationship between variables. This definition of co-integration makes the term a very vital and ideal technique for analyzing and ascertaining the existence of a long-run relationship between the Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates. As asserted by Engle and Granger⁷⁰ (1987), if cointegration is found between two variables, then there must be causal relation between them, either uni-directionally or bi-directionally. Sequel to this, the cointegration test also

provides possible crosscheck on the validity of the results obtained from VAR model for integrated series..

According to Engle and Granger⁷⁰ (1987), the first step in testing cointegration is to test the null hypothesis of a unit root in each component series y_t individually using the unit test discussed in the preceding section. If the hypothesis is not rejected, then the next step is to test cointegration among the component series, that is, to test whether

$$\mathbf{X}_t = \boldsymbol{\beta}' \mathbf{Y}_t \quad (3.60)$$

is stationary for some matrix or vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}'$. Sometimes the choice of the matrix/vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}'$ is based on some theoretical considerations. For example, if

$$\mathbf{Y}_t = [Y_{1,t}, Y_{2,t}]' \quad (3.61)$$

where $Y_{1,t}$ represents revenue and $Y_{2,t}$ represents expenditure, interest may be to test whether the revenues and expenditures are in some long-run equilibrium relation and therefore whether $X_t = Y_{1,t} - Y_{2,t}$ is stationary. In such case, an ideal decision is to choose

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}' = [\mathbf{1} \quad -\mathbf{1}]. \quad (3.62)$$

In testing for cointegration in \mathbf{Y}_t with known cointegrating vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}'$, a null hypothesis formulated to test whether the process $\mathbf{X}_t = \boldsymbol{\beta}' \mathbf{Y}_t$ contains a unit root so that the test discussed in preceding section above can be applicable here. Conclusion is that \mathbf{Y}_t is cointegrated if the null hypothesis is rejected.

When the cointegrating vector is unknown, the following methods are used to test and estimate the cointegration.

(a.) The Regression Method

First note that if the m -dimensional vector process $\mathbf{Y}_t' = [Y_{1,t}, Y_{2,t}, \dots, Y_{m,t}]$ is cointegrated, then there is a nonzero $m \times 1$ vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}' = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m]$ such that $\boldsymbol{\beta}' \mathbf{Y}_t$ is stationary. With no loss of generality, say, $c_1 \neq 0$. Then $(1/c_1)\boldsymbol{\beta}'$ is also a cointegrating vector. Thus, a very natural approach that was also suggested by Engle and Granger⁷⁰ (1987) to test and estimate cointegration is to consider the regression model for $Y_{1,t}$

$$Y_{1,t} = \phi_1 Y_{2,t} + \dots + \phi_{m-1} Y_{m,t} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.63)$$

and check whether the error series ε_t is $I(1)$ or $I(0)$. If ε_t is $I(1)$ and contains a unit root, then Y_t cannot be cointegrated. Otherwise, if ε_t is $I(0)$, then Y_t is cointegrated with a normalizing cointegrating vector $\beta' = [1, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_m]$. The results remain the same for the above model with a constant term included. In drawing inferences using the OLS estimated model, the following should be noted:

a. In testing the error series for nonstationarity, the OLS estimate is calculated,

$$\hat{\beta}' = [1, \hat{\phi}_1, \hat{\phi}_2, \dots, \hat{\phi}_m] \text{ and the residual series } \hat{\varepsilon}_t \text{ is used for the test.}$$

b. The estimates $\hat{\phi}_i$ do not have asymptotic t -distributions, and the standard t -test for $\phi_i = 0$ is not applicable unless ε_t is $I(0)$. The regression in (3.63) will produce a spurious regression if the ε_t is nonstationary.

To test whether the error series ε_t is $I(1)$, we make use of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test in (3.21) and test the null hypothesis

$$H_0: \gamma = 1$$

against

$$H_1: \gamma < 1$$

for the model

$$\varepsilon_t = \gamma \varepsilon_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \gamma_j \Delta \varepsilon_{t-j} + a_t \quad (3.64)$$

Or equivalently, test the null hypothesis

$$H_0: \phi = 0$$

against

$$H_1: \phi < 0$$

for the model

$$\Delta \varepsilon_t = \phi \varepsilon_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \gamma_j \Delta \varepsilon_{t-j} + a_t \quad (3.65)$$

To adjust for the difference in (3.65), the t -statistic, $T = \hat{\varphi}/S_{\hat{\varphi}}$ is compared with the critical values of Monte Carlo experiment performed by Engle and Granger (1987) instead of using the standard Dickey-Fuller tables. Reject the null hypothesis if the T -value is less than the critical value and conclude that cointegration exists among the variables (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

(b.) The Likelihood Ratio Test

Now consider a vector autoregressive process of finite order p

$$Y_t = A_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.66)$$

which can be written as

$$Y_t = \sum_{j=1}^p A_j Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.67)$$

where ε_t denotes a normally distributed k -dimensional white noise process, A_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ are the $k \times k$ -dimensional parameter matrices. The reparameterization as a vector error-correction model leads to

$$\Delta Y_t = -\Pi Y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} A_j^* \Delta Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.68)$$

with

$$\Pi = A(1) = I - \sum_{j=1}^p A_j \quad \text{and} \quad A_j^* = -\sum_{i=j+1}^p A_i, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, p-1$$

The matrix Π represents the long-run relations between the variables. Since all components of Y_t are $I(1)$ variables, each component of $\Delta Y_t, \dots, \Delta Y_{t-p+1}$ is stationary and each component of Y_{t-1} is also integrated of order one. This makes (3.68) unbalanced as long as Π has a full rank of k . In this case the inverse matrix Π^{-1} exists and we could solve (3.68) for Y_{t-1} as a linear combination of stationary variables. However, this would be a contradiction. Therefore, Π must have a reduced rank of $r < k$. Then the following decomposition exists:

$$\begin{matrix} \Pi & = & \Gamma & B' \\ (k \times k) & & (k \times r) & (r \times k) \end{matrix} \quad (3.69)$$

where all matrices have rank r . $B'Y_{t-1}$ are r stationary linear combinations which ensure that the system of equations in (3.68) are balanced. The columns of B contain the r linearly independent cointegration vectors and the matrix Γ contains the so-called loading coefficients which measure the contributions of the r long-run relations in the different equations of the system. The adjustment processes to the equilibria can be derived from these coefficients.

If there is no cointegration, i.e. if $r = 0$, Π is the zero matrix and (3.68) is a VAR of $p - 1$ in ΔY . This system possesses k unit roots, i.e. k stochastic trends. If $r = k - 1$, the system contains exactly one common stochastic trend and all the variables of the system are pair-wise cointegrated. As a general rule, the system (3.68) contains $k - r$ common stochastic trend and r linearly independent cointegration vectors for a cointegration rank r with $0 < r < k$.

The approach proposed by Johansen⁷¹ (1988) is a maximum likelihood estimation of (3.68) that considers the restriction (3.69). We can write

$$\Delta Y_t + \Gamma B'Y_{t-1} = A_1^* \Delta Y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p^* \Delta Y_{t-p+1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.70)$$

The maximum likelihood estimation of $A_j^*, j = 1, \dots, p - 1$, is obtained by applying ordinary least squares on (3.68) if Γ and B are given. Eliminating the influence of the short-run dynamics on ΔY_t and Y_{t-1} by regressing ΔY_t on the lagged differences and Y_{t-1} on the lagged differences, we get the residuals R_{0t} and R_{1t} respectively for which

$$R_{0t} = -\Gamma B' R_{1t} + \hat{\varepsilon}_t \quad (3.71)$$

holds.

Here, R_0 is a vector of stationary and R_1 a vector of nonstationary processes. The idea of the Johansen approach is to find those linear combinations $B'R_1$ which show the highest correlations with R_0 . The optimal values of Γ and the variance-covariance matrix Σ of ε can be derived for known B by ordinary least squares estimation of (3.70). Given that

$$\hat{\Gamma}(B) = -S_{01}B(B'S_{11}B)^{-1} \quad (3.72)$$

and

$$\widehat{\Sigma}(B) = S_{00} - S_{01}B(B'S_{11}B)^{-1}B'S_{10} \quad (3.73)$$

with

$$S_{ij} = T^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^T R_{i,t}R'_{j,t} \quad \text{for } i, j = 0, 1. \quad (3.74)$$

It can be shown that the likelihood function concentrated with (3.72) and (3.73) is proportional to $|\widehat{\Sigma}(B)|^{-T/2}$. Therefore, the optimal values of B result from minimizing the determinant

$$|S_{00} - S_{01}B(B'S_{11}B)^{-1}B'S_{10}|$$

Shown that this is equivalent to the solution of the following eigenvalue problem

$$|\lambda S_{11} - S_{10}S_{00}^{-1}S_{01}| = 0 \quad (3.75)$$

with the eigenvalues λ_i and the corresponding k -dimensional eigenvectors v_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$,

for which

$$\lambda_i S_{11} v_i = S_{10} S_{00}^{-1} S_{01} v_i$$

Using the arbitrary normalization

$$\begin{bmatrix} v'_1 \\ \vdots \\ v'_k \end{bmatrix} S_{11} [v_1 \quad \dots \quad v_k] = I_k ,$$

with I_k being the k -dimensional identity matrix, leads to a unique solution. $1 \geq \hat{\lambda}_1 \geq \dots \geq \hat{\lambda}_k \geq 0$ holds for the ordered estimated eigenvalues. It can be shown that for $k I(1)$ variables with cointegration rank r exactly r eigenvalues are positive and the remaining $k - r$ eigenvalues are asymptotically zero. The cointegrating vectors are estimated by the corresponding eigenvectors and combined in the $k \times r$ matrix

$$\widehat{B} = [\hat{v}_1 \quad \dots \quad \hat{v}_r] ,$$

The number of significantly positive eigenvalues determines the rank r of the cointegration space. This leads to two different likelihood ratio test procedures:

i. The so called trace test has the null hypothesis

$$H_0: \text{There are at most } r \text{ positive eigenvalues}$$

against the alternative hypothesis that there are more than r positive eigenvalues. The test statistic is given by

$$Tr(r) = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^k \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_i) \quad (3.76)$$

ii. The so-called λ_{max} test analyses whether there are r or $r + 1$ cointegrating vectors. The null hypothesis is

H_0 : There are exactly r positive eigenvalues

against the alternative hypothesis that there are exactly $r + 1$ positive eigenvalues. The corresponding test statistic is given by

$$\lambda_{max}(r, r + 1) = -T \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_{r+1}) \quad (3.77)$$

The series of tests starts with $r = 0$ and is performed until the first time the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. The cointegration rank is given by the corresponding value of r . The null hypothesis is rejected for too large values of the test statistic. Since the test statistics do not follow standard asymptotic distributions, the critical values are generated by simulations (Kirchgassner and Wolter⁵⁶ 2007).

The distribution of these tests is a mixture of functional Brownian motions that are calculated through numerical simulation by Johansen⁷² (1995) and Osterwald-Lenum⁷³ (1992). For small samples, Johansen's λ_{max} and λ_{trace} statistics are sensitive to under parameterization of the lag length but not sensitive to over parameterization (Cheung and Lai⁷⁴, 1993).

3.4.21 Covariance and Correlation Matrix Functions

Let $\mathbf{X} = (X_{1t}, X_{2t}, \dots, X_{nt})'$, $t = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ be an n -dimensional jointly real-valued vector process so that mean $E(X_{it}) = \mu_i$ is a constant for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and the cross-covariance between X_{it} and X_{js} , $\forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are functions only of the time lag $(s - t)$. Hence, we have mean vector

$$E(\mathbf{X}_t) = \boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_n)' \quad (3.78)$$

and the k th lag covariance matrix

$$\Gamma(k) = \text{Cov}(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{X}_{t+k}) = E[(\mathbf{X}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu})(\mathbf{X}_{t+k} - \boldsymbol{\mu})'] \quad (3.79)$$

$$= E \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} X_{1t} - \mu_1 \\ X_{2t} - \mu_2 \\ \vdots \\ X_{nt} - \mu_n \end{bmatrix} [X_{1t+k} - \mu_1, X_{2t+k} - \mu_2, \dots, X_{nt+k} - \mu_n] \right\}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{11}(k) & \gamma_{12}(k) & \dots & \gamma_{1n}(k) \\ \gamma_{21}(k) & \gamma_{22}(k) & \dots & \gamma_{2n}(k) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \gamma_{n1}(k) & \gamma_{n2}(k) & \dots & \gamma_{nn}(k) \end{bmatrix} = \text{Cov}(\mathbf{X}_{t-k}, \mathbf{X}_t)$$

where

$$\gamma_{ij}(k) = E[(X_{it} - \mu_i)(X_{jt+k} - \mu_j)] = E[(X_{it-k} - \mu_i)(X_{jt} - \mu_j)]$$

for $k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

As a function of k , $\Gamma(k)$ is called the covariance matrix function for the vector process \mathbf{X}_t .

$\gamma_{ii}(k)$ is the autocovariance function for the i th component process X_{it} and $\gamma_{ij}(k)$ is the cross-covariance function for the vector process.

The autocorrelation matrix function process is defined by

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}(k) = \mathbf{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \Gamma(k) \mathbf{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} = [\rho_{ij}(k)], \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where \mathbf{D} is the diagonal matrix in which the i th diagonal element is the variance of the i th process. That is,

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}[\gamma_{11}(0), \gamma_{22}(0), \dots, \gamma_{nn}(0)] \quad (3.80)$$

Clearly, the i th diagonal element of $\boldsymbol{\rho}(k)$, $\rho_{ii}(k)$, is the autocorrelation function for the i th component series X_{it} , whereas the (i, j) th off-diagonal element of $\boldsymbol{\rho}(k)$, represent the cross-correlation function between X_{it} and X_{jt} , thus

$$\rho_{ij}(k) = \frac{\gamma_{ij}(k)}{[\gamma_{ii}(0)\gamma_{jj}(0)]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (3.81)$$

Covariance and correlation matrix functions are positive semi-definite, that is,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i' \Gamma(t_i - t_j) \alpha_j \geq 0 \quad (3.82)$$

for any set of time points t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n and any set of real vectors $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$

$$\gamma_{ij}(k) \neq \gamma_{ij}(-k) \text{ for } i \neq j \text{ and } \Gamma(k) \neq \Gamma(-k)$$

$$\gamma_{ij}(k) = E[(X_{it} - \mu_i)(X_{jt+k} - \mu_j)] = E[(X_{it-k} - \mu_i)(X_{jt} - \mu_j)] = \gamma_{ji}(k),$$

we have $\Gamma(k) = \Gamma'(-k)$ and $\rho(k) = \rho'(-k)$

The sample covariance matrix is

$$\hat{\Gamma}(k) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^{n-k} [(X_{it} - \bar{X}_i)(X_{jt+k} - \bar{X}_j)] \quad (3.83)$$

Given a vector time series of n observations $X_{1t}, X_{2t}, \dots, X_{nt}$, the sample correlation matrix function can be calculated with

$$\hat{\rho}_{ij}(k) = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{n-k} [(X_{it} - \bar{X}_i)(X_{jt+k} - \bar{X}_j)]}{\left[\sum_{t=1}^n (X_{it} - \bar{X}_i)^2 (X_{jt+k} - \bar{X}_j)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (3.84)$$

where $\hat{\rho}_{ij}(k)$ are the cross-correlations for the i th and j th component series. \bar{X}_i and \bar{X}_j are the sample means of the corresponding series.

For a stationary vector process, $\hat{\rho}_{ij}(k)$ is a consistent estimator that is asymptotically normally distributed, see for example Hannan⁷⁵ (1970).

3.4.22 Vector Autoregressive Model

A vector autoregressive is a system in which each variable is regressed on a constant and p of its own lags as well as on p lags of each of the other variables in the vector autoregressive model (VAR) model (Hamilton⁷⁶, 1994).

3.4.23 Stationary Vector Autoregressive Model

Let $\mathbf{X} = (X_{1t}, X_{2t}, \dots, X_{nt})'$ denote $(n \times 1)$ vector of times series variables. The p th-order vector autoregressive model denoted by $VAR(p)$ has the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_{1t} \\ X_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ X_{nt} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11}^1 & \phi_{12}^1 & \cdots & \phi_{1n}^1 \\ \phi_{21}^1 & \phi_{22}^1 & \cdots & \phi_{2n}^1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi_{n1}^1 & \phi_{n2}^1 & \cdots & \phi_{nn}^1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{1t-1} \\ X_{2t-1} \\ \vdots \\ X_{nt-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11}^2 & \phi_{12}^2 & \cdots & \phi_{1n}^2 \\ \phi_{21}^2 & \phi_{22}^2 & \cdots & \phi_{2n}^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi_{n1}^2 & \phi_{n2}^2 & \cdots & \phi_{nn}^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{1t-2} \\ X_{2t-2} \\ \vdots \\ X_{nt-2} \end{bmatrix} + \cdots +$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11}^p & \phi_{12}^p & \cdots & \phi_{1n}^p \\ \phi_{21}^p & \phi_{22}^p & \cdots & \phi_{2n}^p \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi_{n1}^p & \phi_{n2}^p & \cdots & \phi_{nn}^p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_{1t-p} \\ X_{2t-p} \\ \vdots \\ X_{nt-p} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1t} \\ \varepsilon_{2t} \\ \vdots \\ \varepsilon_{nt} \end{bmatrix}$$

In matrix notation

$$\mathbf{X}_t = \mathbf{C} + \phi_1 \mathbf{X}_{t-1} + \phi_2 \mathbf{X}_{t-2} + \cdots + \phi_p \mathbf{X}_{t-p} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t \quad (3.85)$$

Here \mathbf{C} denotes an $(n \times 1)$ vector of constants and ϕ_j an $(n \times n)$ matrix of coefficients for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$. The $(n \times 1)$ vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t$ is a vector of vector generalization of white noise (Hamilton⁷⁶, 1994).

$$E(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t) = \mathbf{0}$$

$$E(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s') = \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\Sigma} & \text{for } t = s \\ \mathbf{0} & \text{for } t \neq s \end{cases} \quad (3.86)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ an $(n \times n)$ symmetric positive definite matrix. This assumption allows for estimation by ordinary least squares because each individual residual series is assumed to be serially uncorrelated with constant variance.

Using lag operator notation, (3.85) can be written in the form

$$[\mathbf{1}_n - \phi_1 \mathbf{L} - \phi_2 \mathbf{L}^2 \dots - \phi_p \mathbf{L}^p] \mathbf{X}_t = \mathbf{C} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t \quad (3.87)$$

Alternatively it can be written as

$$\phi(\mathbf{L}) \mathbf{X}_t = \mathbf{C} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t \quad (3.88)$$

Here $\phi(\mathbf{L})$ is an $(n \times n)$ matrix polynomial in the lag operator \mathbf{L} . Vector autoregressive is a covariance-stationary if all values \mathbf{z} satisfying $|\mathbf{1}_n - \phi_1 \mathbf{z} - \phi_2 \mathbf{z}^2 \dots - \phi_p \mathbf{z}^p| = 0$ lie outside the unit circle. If the process is covariance-stationary, we can take expectations of both sides of (3.85) to calculate the mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ of the process (Hamilton⁷⁶, 1994).

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \mathbf{C} + \phi_1 \boldsymbol{\mu} + \phi_2 \boldsymbol{\mu} + \dots + \phi_p \boldsymbol{\mu}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mathbf{1}_n - \phi_1 - \phi_2 \dots - \phi_p]^{-1} \mathbf{C} \quad (3.89)$$

A jointly stationary process implies that every univariate component process is stationary. A vector of univariate stationary processes, however, is not necessarily a jointly stationary vector process (Wei⁵⁸, 2006).

3.4.24 Covariance and Correlation Matrices of the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Process

Suppose \mathbf{X}_t is a stationary VAR(1) model

$$\mathbf{X}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \phi_1 \mathbf{X}_{t-1} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t$$

$$\mathbf{X}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu} = \phi_1 \mathbf{X}_{t-1} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t \quad (3.90)$$

with white noise covariance matrix

$$E(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_t') = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon$$

Post multiplying (3.90) by $(\mathbf{X}_{t+k} - \boldsymbol{\mu})'$ and taking the expectations gives

$$E[(\mathbf{X}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu})(\mathbf{X}_{t+k} - \boldsymbol{\mu})'] = \text{Cov}(\mathbf{X}_t, \mathbf{X}_{t+k}) = \Gamma(k)$$

Thus, for $k = 0$

$$\Gamma(0) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(-1) + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma'(1) + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon \quad (3.91)$$

since $\Gamma(-1) = \Gamma'(1)$

and for $k > 0$

$$\Gamma(k) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(k-1) \quad (3.92)$$

These equations are usually referred to as Yule-Walker equations. If $\boldsymbol{\phi}_1$ and covariance matrix $\Gamma(0)$ are known, $\Gamma(k)$ can be computed recursively using (3.92).

If $\boldsymbol{\phi}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon$ are given, $\Gamma(0)$ can be determined using (3.92) as follows;

$$k = 1; \Gamma(1) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(0)$$

Substituting $\Gamma(1) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(0)$ in (3.91), then

$$\Gamma(0) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(0) \boldsymbol{\phi}_1' + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon$$

And generally, for $VAR(p)$ model when $k = 0$

$$\Gamma(0) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(-1) + \dots + \boldsymbol{\phi}_p \Gamma(-p) + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon$$

$$\Gamma(0) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma'(1) + \dots + \boldsymbol{\phi}_p \Gamma'(p) + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon \quad (3.93)$$

and for $k > 0$,

$$\Gamma(k) = \boldsymbol{\phi}_1 \Gamma(k-1) + \dots + \boldsymbol{\phi}_p \Gamma(k-p) \quad (3.94)$$

Given the matrices $\Gamma(0), \Gamma(1), \dots, \Gamma(k)$, equation (3.94) can be used to determine the coefficient matrices $\boldsymbol{\phi}_1, \boldsymbol{\phi}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\phi}_p$. The white noise covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon$ can be found from (3.74). The Yule-Walker estimators $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}_1, \hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}_2, \dots, \hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}}_p$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_\varepsilon$ for $VAR(p)$ model fitted to the data $\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2, \dots, \mathbf{X}_n$ are obtained by replacing $\Gamma(k)$ in (3.93) and (3.94) with $\hat{\Gamma}(k)$, $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p$ and solving the resulting equations for $\boldsymbol{\phi}_1, \boldsymbol{\phi}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\phi}_p$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varepsilon$.

The covariance matrix function of the $VAR(p)$ process is obtained using (3.93).

3.4.25 Determination of Optimal Lag Length for the VAR Model

The robustness of the inferences made on any VAR model principally anchors on the adequacy or the optimality of the lag length. According to Gujarati⁷⁷ (2004), choosing the appropriate lag length is the biggest practical problem in VAR modelling. The specification of a proper dynamic structure is a crucial preliminary step in univariate or multivariate ARMA type time series models. Although the determination of a proper lag structure is seldom of individual interest or the final objective of the empirical investigation. It has a great impact on subsequent inferences whether they are about causality, co-integration, impulse response analysis or forecasting (Gonzalo and Pitarakis⁷⁸, 2002).

- a. If the lag length p is too small, then the remaining serial correlation in the errors will make the test bias.
- b. If the lag length is too large, then the power of the test will suffer.
- c. Monte Carlo experiments suggest it is better to commit an error on the side of including many lags, i.e. it is safer to over fit the model instead of under fitting (Ng and Perron⁷⁹, 2001).

The following are the frequently used lag length selection criteria;

Akaike Information Criteria (AIC), (Akaike⁸⁰, 1974)

Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC), (Schwarz⁸¹, 1978)

Hannan-Quinn Information Criteria (HQ), (Hannan and Quinn⁸³, 1979).

For a $VAR(p)$ process, the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) is defined by

$$AIC(P) = \ln|\hat{\Sigma}(p)| + \frac{2}{T}PK^2 \quad (3.95)$$

The estimate $\hat{p}(AIC)$ for p is chosen so that this criterion is minimized for $p = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

The Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) or Schwarz Information Criteria is given by

$$BIC(P) = \ln|\hat{\Sigma}(p)| + \frac{\ln T}{T}PK^2 \quad (3.96)$$

The estimate $\hat{p}(BIC)$ for p is chosen so that this criterion is minimized for $p = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

And the Hannan-Quinn Information Criteria (HQ) is given by

$$HQ(P) = \ln|\hat{\Sigma}(p)| + \frac{2\ln\ln T}{T} PK^2 \quad (3.97)$$

The estimate $\hat{p}(HQ)$ for p is chosen so that this criterion is minimized for $p = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

In each case, $\psi(K, P) = PK^2$ is the number of VAR parameters in the model of order p and $\hat{\Sigma}(p) = T^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^T \hat{\varepsilon}_t \hat{\varepsilon}_t'$ is the maximum likelihood estimate of Σ_ε obtained by fitting the VAR model. The AIC criterion asymptotically over estimates the order with positive probability, whereas, the BIC and HQ criteria estimate the order consistently under fairly general conditions if the order of p is less than or equal to P_{max} . Where P_{max} is the maximum lag order to be included in the system.

3.4.26 Diagnostic Checking of VAR Models

To avoid misspecification, the VAR models should be checked and crosschecked before they are used for any specific purpose in order to ensure that the model fit the data adequately. Some of the areas to look into are the inverse root of the AR polynomial; the roots must lie within the unit circle before stability condition is met. Other analyses to guard against model misspecification include plots of standardized residuals against time and the analysis of residual correlation matrices. Various tests are prescribed for testing the autocorrelation of the residuals. Two of the most widely used tests are: Portmanteau test, LaGrange Multiplier (LM) test.

(a.) Portmanteau Test

Portmanteau test can be implemented only when the order of autocorrelation is higher than the lag length in the VAR model. It tests the overall significance of the residual autocorrelations of a $VAR(P)$ model up to lag s . The null hypothesis of no multivariate residual autocorrelation of degree s is

$H_0: \mathbf{B}_1 = \mathbf{B}_2 = \dots = \mathbf{B}_s = \mathbf{0}$ and the alternative hypothesis is

$H_1: \text{The } \mathbf{B}_i \text{'s not all } 0$

where \mathbf{B}_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, s$) are the autocorrelation matrices.

The test statistic for large T is

$$\mathbf{Q}_s = T \sum_{i=1}^s \text{tr}(\widehat{\mathbf{C}}_i' \widehat{\mathbf{C}}_0^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{C}}_i \widehat{\mathbf{C}}_0^{-1}) \quad (3.98)$$

Therefore, the modified test statistic (especially in small samples) is

$$\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_s = T^2 \sum_{i=1}^s (T-i)^{-1} \text{tr}(\widehat{\mathbf{C}}_i' \widehat{\mathbf{C}}_0^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{C}}_i \widehat{\mathbf{C}}_0^{-1}) \quad (3.99)$$

$\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_s$ has the same asymptotic distribution as \mathbf{Q}_s , that is, approximately in large samples and for large s ,

$$\bar{\mathbf{Q}}_s \approx \chi_{\alpha, [K^2(s-p)]}^2 \quad (3.100)$$

where K is the dimension of the time series and $\widehat{\mathbf{C}}_i$ are the estimated autocovariance matrices of the residuals and $\widehat{\mathbf{C}}_0$ the estimated variance of the residuals.

(b.) LaGrange Multiplier (LM) Test

Unlike Portmanteau test, LaGrange Multiplier (LM) Test can be implemented not only when the order of autocorrelation is higher than the lag length in the VAR model. It test residual serial correlation in a $VAR(P)$ model up to lag s .

The null hypothesis of no multivariate residual serial correlation of degree s is

$H_0: \mathbf{B}_1 = \mathbf{B}_2 = \dots = \mathbf{B}_s = \mathbf{0}$ and the alternative hypothesis is

$H_1: \text{The } \mathbf{B}_i \text{'s not all } 0$

where \mathbf{B}_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, s$) are the autocorrelation matrices.

The test statistic is

$$LM = n \left(\mathbf{i}' \widehat{\mathbf{G}}_R [\widehat{\mathbf{G}}_R' \widehat{\mathbf{G}}_R]^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{G}}_R' \mathbf{i} / n \right) = nR_i^2 \quad (3.101)$$

which is n times the uncentered squared multiple correlation coefficient in a linear regression of a column of 1s on the derivatives of the log-likelihood function computed at the restricted estimator.

where

$$\widehat{\mathbf{G}}_R' \mathbf{i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \widehat{\mathbf{g}}_{iR} = \widehat{\mathbf{g}}_R = \frac{\partial \ln L(\widehat{\theta}_R)}{\partial \widehat{\theta}_R} \quad (3.102)$$

$$LM \approx \chi_{\alpha, [K^2(s-p)]}^2$$

where K is the dimension of the time series, s is the order of autocorrelation and p is the lag length in the VAR model.

3.4.27 Forecasting

Forecasting is one of the main objectives of multivariate time series analysis. Forecasting from a VAR model is similar to forecasting from a univariate AR model.

If we consider forecasting the future values of \mathbf{X}_t when the parameter matrices Π of the $VAR(p)$ process are assumed to be known and there are no deterministic terms or exogenous variables. The best linear predictor, in terms of minimum mean squared error (MSE), of \mathbf{X}_{t+l} or the l -step forecast based on information available at time T is

$$\mathbf{X}_{T+1|T} = \mathbf{c} + \Pi_1 \mathbf{X}_T + \cdots + \Pi_p \mathbf{X}_{T-p+1} \quad (3.103)$$

Forecast for longer horizons h (h -step forecasts) may be obtained using the chain-rule of forecasting as

$$\mathbf{X}_{T+h|T} = \mathbf{c} + \Pi_1 \mathbf{X}_{T+h-1|T} + \cdots + \Pi_p \mathbf{X}_{T+h-p|T} \quad (3.104)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_{T+j|T} = \mathbf{X}_{T+j}$ for $j \leq 0$. The h -step forecast errors may be expressed as

$$\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \mathbf{X}_{T+h|T} = \sum_{s=0}^{h-1} \Psi_s \epsilon_{T+h-s} \quad (3.105)$$

where the matrices Ψ_s are determined by recursive substitution

$$\Psi_s = \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \Psi_{s-j} \Pi_j \quad (3.106)$$

with $\Psi_0 = \mathbf{I}_n$ and $\Pi_j = 0$ for $j > p$. The forecasts are unbiased since all of the forecast errors have expectation zero and the MSE matrix for $\mathbf{X}_{T+h|T}$ is

$$\Sigma(h) = MSE(\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \mathbf{X}_{T+h|T}) \quad (3.107)$$

$$= \sum_{s=0}^{h-1} \Psi_s \Sigma \Psi_s' \quad (3.108)$$

Now, if we consider forecasting \mathbf{X}_{T+h} when the parameters of the $VAR(p)$ process are estimated using multivariate least squares. The best linear predictor of \mathbf{X}_{T+h} is now

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T} = \mathbf{c} + \widehat{\Pi}_1 \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h-1|T} + \cdots + \widehat{\Pi}_p \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h-p|T} \quad (3.109)$$

where $\widehat{\Pi}_j$ are the estimated parameter matrices. The h -step forecast error is now

$$\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T} = \sum_{s=0}^{h-1} \boldsymbol{\Psi}_s \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{T+h-s} + (\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T}) \quad (3.110)$$

and the term $(\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T})$ captures the part of the forecast error due to estimating the parameters of the VAR. the MSE matrix of the h -step forecast is then

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}(h) = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(h) + \text{MSE}(\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T}) \quad (3.111)$$

In practice, the second term $\text{MSE}(\mathbf{X}_{T+h} - \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T})$ is often ignored and $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}(h)$ is computed using (3.108) as

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}(h) = \sum_{s=0}^{h-1} \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_s \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_s' \quad (3.112)$$

with $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_s = \sum_{j=0}^{s-1} \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{s-j} \widehat{\Pi}_j$. Asymptotic $(1 - \alpha) \cdot 100\%$ confidence intervals for the individual elements of $\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_{T+h|T}$ are computed as

$$[\hat{y}_{k,T+h|T} - c_{1-\alpha/2} \hat{\sigma}_k(h), \hat{y}_{k,T+h|T} + c_{1-\alpha/2} \hat{\sigma}_k(h)]$$

where $c_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the $(1 - \alpha/2)$ quantile of the standard normal distribution and $\hat{\sigma}_k(h)$ denotes the square root of the diagonal element of $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}(h)$.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the results of the findings are presented as obtained from the methods prescribed by the preceded chapter, interpret results and also discuss the implication of these results.

4.1.1 Preliminary Analysis

(a.) Crude Oil Prices

(i) Time Series Plots

From the plots of the series (Appendix XXIX), the series appears to be monotonic increasing. It seems to increase at a considerably steady rate between 1995:1 and 2006:12 and increase to all time high values between 2007:1 and 2008:6 before falling drastically between 2008:7 and 2008:12. This sharp drift between 2007/2008 may be due to the effect of global financial crisis of that period. The series later increase with greater gyrations between 2009:1 and 2014:6 before dropping again, possibly due to the depreciation in global oil prices of 2014. On the whole, the series exhibits slower gyrations at the beginning till about 2007 before the swing became more pronounced even to the ending part. The plot of the series also exhibits a curvy shape that looks like that of an exponential function which suggests that it may require a variance stabilizing transformation like the log. After the natural logarithm of the series was taken as shown in Appendix XXX, it is noticed that the swings and the curvy shape have reduced considerably and by this enhance the modelling of the time series variables. The log of the series is used for modelling.

(ii) Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function

The plot of the Autocorrelation Functions (ACF) and the Partial Autocorrelation Functions (PACF) of the log of crude oil prices is presented in Appendix XXXI. The autocorrelation

functions plots which die out slowly even at high lags is a clear indication of nonstationarity of the variable.

(iii) Unit Root Tests for Stationarity

The unit root test result is presented in Appendix I for log of Crude Oil Price and Appendix II presents the unit root test for log of Crude Oil Price at first difference. The result shows that the variable is integrated of order 1 since it is stationary at first difference. This test is a complementary analysis to the Autocorrelation Partial Autocorrelation Functions for ascertaining stationarity.

With maximum lag length of 14, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic value for the log of Crude Oil Prices is -1.407061 and the test critical values are -3.457865 , -2.873543 and -2.573242 at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively. Since the test critical values are all less than the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic at 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted and conclusion is that the Crude Oil Prices is non-stationary. The MacKinnon⁸³ (1996) one-sided p-value of 0.5786 further confirms this claim. A first difference of the series is considered, at first difference the ADF test statistic for the Crude Oil Prices is -11.192460 while the test critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance are respectively -3.457865 , -2.873543 and -2.573242 . At this point, since the test critical values are all greater than the ADF test statistic and the MacKinnon⁸³ (1996) one-sided p-value of the possibility of the null hypothesis happening is 0.0000, then it is concluded that the Crude Oil Price is stationary at first difference, i.e. $q_i = 1$.

(b.) Market Capitalization

(i) Time Series Plots

From the plots of the series (Appendix XXIX), just like the preceding, the series appears to be monotonic increasing. It seems to increase at a considerably steady rate between 1995:1 and 2006:12 and increase to all time high values between 2007:1 and 2008:6 before falling drastically between 2008:7 and 2008:12. This sharp drift between 2007/2008 may be due to the effect of global financial crisis of that period. The series later increase with greater

gyrations between 2009:1 and 2014:6 before dropping again, possibly due to the depreciation in global oil prices of 2014. On the whole, the series exhibits slower gyrations at the beginning till about 2007 before the swing became more pronounced even to the ending part. The plot of the series also exhibits a curvy shape that looks like that of an exponential function which suggests that the series may require a variance stabilizing transformation like the log. After the natural logarithm of the series was taken as shown in Appendix XXX, it is noticed that the swings and high gyrations reduced considerably and by this enhance the modelling of the time series variables. We adopt the log of the series for the analysis.

(ii) Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function

The plot of the Autocorrelation Functions (ACF) and the Partial Autocorrelation Functions (PACF) of the log of the market capitalization is presented in Appendix XXXII. The autocorrelation functions which die out slowly even at high lags is a clear indication of nonstationarity of the variable.

(iii) Unit Root Tests for Stationarity

The unit root test result is presented in Appendix III for the log of market capitalization and Appendix IV presents the unit root test for log of Market Capitalization at first difference. The result show that the variable is integrated of order 1 since it is stationary at first difference.

With maximum lag length of 14, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic value for the log of Market Capitalization, the ADF test statistic is -1.292262 while the test critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance are -3.457747 , -2.873492 and -2.573215 respectively. Since the test critical values are all less than the ADF test statistic, the null hypothesis is accepted and conclusion is that the series has a unit root at level. The MacKinnon⁸³ (1996) one-sided p-value of 0.6336 confirms that the series is non-stationary. A first difference of the series is considered, at first difference the Market Capitalization is stationary since the ADF test statistic of -13.60999 is less than the test critical values of -3.457865 , -2.873543 and -2.573242 at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance

respectively. The MacKinnon⁸³ (1996) one-sided p-value of 0.0000 confirms this claim. Here $q_j = 1$.

(c.) Exchange Rate

(i) Time Series Plots

From the plots of the series Appendix XXIX, the series appears to be monotonic increasing. It increases at a faster rate between 1995 and 2003 and afterward moves at a very slow rate between 2003 and 2007. It dropped briefly in 2007 and later increase between 2008 and 2009. The series then increases rapidly between 2009 and 2011. A recess is observed in the series between 2011 and 2014 and again an increase in the later part of 2014.

Though the shocks are not really pronounced in this series, a variance stabilizing transformation like the log may not really create much impact on the series. But for uniformity sake, natural logarithm of the series was taken as shown in Appendix XXX.

(ii) Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function

The plot of the Autocorrelation Functions (ACF) and the Partial Autocorrelation Functions (PACF) of the log of Exchange Rate is presented in Appendix XXXIII. The autocorrelation functions which die out slowly even at high lags is a clear indication of nonstationarity of the variable.

(iii) Unit Root Tests for Stationarity

The unit root test result is presented in Appendix V for the log of Exchange Rate and Appendix VI presents the unit root test for log of Exchange Rate at first difference. The result show that the variable is integrated of order 1 since it is stationary at first difference.

With maximum lag length of, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic value for the log of Exchange Rates, the ADF test statistic is -1.102509 while the test critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance are -3.457865 , -2.8737543 and -2.573242 respectively. Since the test critical values are all less than the ADF test statistic, the null hypothesis is accepted and conclusion is that the log of Exchange Rate has a unit root. The MacKinnon⁸³ (1996) one-sided p-value of 0.7152 confirms that the series is non-stationary. A

first difference of the series is considered, at first difference the Exchange Rates is stationary since the ADF test statistic of -10.81530 is less than the test critical values of -3.457865 , -2.8737543 and -2.573242 respectively. The MacKinnon⁸³ (1996) one-sided p-value of 0.0000 confirms this claim. Here $q_k = 1$.

4.2 Univariate Time Series Modelling of the Variables

In modelling the time series variables as univariates, the following steps are taken:

4.2.1 Crude Oil Prices

(a.) Model Identification

The first difference of the log of the series is plotted in Appendix XXXIV. The correlogram of the log of the first difference up to lag 48 is given in Appendix XXXV. From the ACF and PACF, some spikes at lag 1 and 13 in the ACF and at lag 1, 13 and 25 in the PACF are noticed. Since the spikes are more pronounced in the PACF, it is suggested that the disturbances may come from the moving average component of the model and this points to $ARIMA(0,1,1)$, $ARIMA(0,1,2)$ and $ARIMA(0,1,25)$ models. Then tentative models are respectively presented in equations (4.1), (4.2), (4.3) and (4.4).

(b.) Estimation of Parameters

The parameters of the $ARIMA(0,1,1)$, $ARIMA(0,1,2)$ models and the two other models deduced from $ARIMA(0,1,25)$ model with their respective standard errors in parentheses are estimated and presented in Appendix VII for model given by equation (4.1), Appendix VIII for model given by equation (4.2), Appendix IX for model in equation (4.3) and Appendix X for model given by equation (4.4) as

$$\nabla \ln COP_t = \varepsilon_t - 0.2064\varepsilon_{t-1} \quad (4.1)$$

(0.0572)

$AIC = -526.9633$, $BIC = -520.0188$ and $HQ = -524.1645$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 52.7368

$$\nabla \ln COP_t = \varepsilon_t - 0.2269\varepsilon_{t-1} - 0.1293\varepsilon_{t-2} \quad (4.2)$$

(0.0640) (0.0652)

$AIC = -528.7677$, $BIC = -518.3509$ and $HQ = -524.5695$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 52.9111

$$\nabla \ln COP_t = \varepsilon_t - 0.2286\varepsilon_{t-1} + 0.1724\varepsilon_{t-13} - 0.1614\varepsilon_{t-25} \quad (4.3)$$

(0.0556607) (0.0652704) (0.0619959)

$AIC = -535.6411$, $BIC = -521.7520$ and $HQ = -530.0435$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 40.2027

$$\nabla \ln COP_t = \varepsilon_t - 0.259\varepsilon_{t-1} - 0.1441\varepsilon_{t-2} + 0.1517\varepsilon_{t-13} - 0.1767\varepsilon_{25} \quad (4.4)$$

(0.0629187) (0.0648282) (0.0629627) (0.0608958)

$AIC = -538.3882$, $BIC = -521.0268$ and $HQ = -531.3913$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 34.9998 .

where COP stands for Crude Oil Prices.

(c.) Diagnostic Checking of the Models

The lone parameter of the first model in equation (4.1) is statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is also used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is observed that the model is adequate since Q-statistic = 52.7368 computed at lag 48 < $\chi^2_{0.05,47} = 64.0011$ with a p value of 0.2619. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XXXVI) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is also observed that most of the coefficients fall inside of the 95% confident interval (-0.125, 0.125); and the 2 coefficients (that is -0.1563 at lag 13 and 0.1431 at lag 25) for ACF and 3 coefficients (that is -0.1999 at lag 13, 0.1790 at lag 25 and -0.1381 at lag 39) for PACF that shift out of bounds are less than or equivalent to 5% of the total lags.

The two parameters of the second model in equation (4.2) are statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is also used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is

observed that the model is adequate since Q-statistic = 52.9111 computed at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,46}^2 = 62.8296$ with a p value of 0.2248. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XXXVII) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is also observed that most of the coefficients fall inside of the 95% confident interval (-0.125, 0.125); and the 2 coefficients (that is -0.1541 at lag 13 and 0.1625 at lag 25) for ACF and 3 coefficients (that is -0.1820 at lag 13, 0.1859 at lag 25 and -0.1410 at lag 39) for PACF that shift out of bounds are less than or equivalent to 5% of the total lags.

The parameters of the third model are statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is also used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is observed that the model is adequate since Q-statistic = 40.2027 computed at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,45}^2 = 61.6562$ with a p value of 0.6750. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XXXVIII) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is also observed that most of the coefficients fall inside of the 95% confident interval (-0.125, 0.125); and the 2 coefficients (that is 0.1334 at lag 2 and -0.1313 at lag 6) for ACF and 2 coefficients (that is 0.1328 at lag 2, and -0.1341 at lag 39) for PACF that shift out of bounds are less than 5% of the total lags.

For the fourth model, all of the parameters are statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is observed that the model is adequate since Q-statistic = 34.9998 computed at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,44}^2 = 60.4809$ with a p-value of 0.8319. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XXXIX) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is also observed that all of the coefficients fall inside of the 95% confident interval (-0.125, 0.125); and 2 coefficients (that is -0.1416 at lag 15, and -0.1317 at lag 39) for PACF that shift out of bounds are less than 5% of the total lags.

All the four models have passed the Portmanteau test for residual autocorrelation. Comparing the values of the information criteria of the four models as shown above, it is noticed that the BIC values for the ARIMA (0,1,1) model in equation (4.1) and the model given by equation (4.4) which has the closest correlogram of residuals to white noise (WN)

$AIC = -571.3059$, $BIC = -547.0000$ and $HQ = -561.5102$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 41.4251 .

where MC stands for Market Capitalization.

c. Diagnostic Checking of the Models

All the parameters of the first model in equation are statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is also used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is observed that the model is adequate since Q-statistic = 51.2231 computed at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,44}^2 = 60.4809$ with a p-value of 0.2114. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XLI) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is also observed that all of the coefficients fall inside of the 95% confident interval (-0.125, 0.125); except 2 coefficients (that is -0.1298 at lag 13, and 0.1476 at lag 32) for ACF and 3 coefficients (that is -0.1348 at lag 25, -0.1438 at lag 29 and 0.1332 at 36) for PACF that shift out of bounds which are less than or equivalent to 5% of the total lags.

For the second model given by equation (4.6), all of the parameters are statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is also used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is observed that the model is adequate since Q-statistic = 41.4251 computed at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,43}^2 = 59.3035$ with a p-value of 0.5397. Using the residual ACF and PACF given by Appendix XLII up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is seen that 2 of the coefficients (that is -0.1380 at lag 21 and -0.1482 at lag 26) for the ACF and just 1 of the coefficients (that is -0.1287 at lag 21) fall outside of the 95% confident interval (-0.125, 0.125) which is less than 5% of the total lag.

Comparing the values of the information criteria of the two models as shown in Appendices XI and XII respectively and the p-values, it is noticed that the *ARIMA*(13,1,29) model in equation (4.6) has lesser values compared to the *ARIMA*(3,1,1) model in equation (4.5) and bigger p-values but based on the principle of parsimony; former model is entertained.

4.2.3 Exchange Rates

a. Model Identification

The first difference of the log of the series is plotted in Appendix XXXIV. The correlogram of the log of the first difference up to lag 48 is given in Appendix XLIII. From the ACF and the PACF, some severe spikes at lag 1 in the ACF and also a spike at lag 1 and a near cut at lag 2 in the PACF are noticed. As a result of the cut at lag 1 in the ACF, an integrated $AR(1)$ model is initiated as one of the tentative models as presented in equation (4.7). Another model that could be seen as a tentative model is $ARIMA(1,1,2)$ model due to the near cut at lag 2. This model is presented in equation (4.8).

b. Estimation of Parameters

The estimated parameters of the integrated $AR(1)$ model presented in Appendix XIII for model in equation (4.7) and $ARIMA(1,1,2)$ model presented in Appendix XIV for model in equation (4.8) with their respective standard errors in parentheses are as follows:

$$(1 - 0.354428L)\nabla \ln ER_t = \varepsilon_t \quad (4.7)$$

(0.060602)

$AIC = -1321.891$, $BIC = -1314.947$ and $HQ = -1319.092$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 48.9782.

$$(1 + 0.754687L)\nabla \ln ER_t = (1 - 1.14785L - 0.347507L^2)\varepsilon_t \quad (4.8)$$

(0.22608) (0.223689) (0.0889898)

$AIC = -1321.179$, $BIC = -1307.290$ and $HQ = -1315.581$; and the Portmanteau Q-statistic = 19.6751.

Where ER stands for Exchange Rates.

c. Diagnostic Checking of the Models

The lone parameter of the first model in equation (4.7) is statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test is used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it is observed

that the model is adequate at 5% level of significance since Q-statistic = 48.9782 computed at lag 48 $< \chi_{0.05,47}^2 = 64.0011$ with a p-value of 0.3936. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XLIV) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it is seen that just 1 of the coefficients (that is 0.1489 at lag 35) in the ACF and 1 of the coefficients (that is -0.1277 at lag 25) in the PACF fall outside of the 95% confident interval $(-0.125, 0.125)$ which is less than 5% of the total number of lags.

For the second model given by equation (4.8), all the parameters are statistically significant. The Portmanteau lack of fit test was also used to confirm the adequacy of this model and it was observed that according the test, the model was adequate since Q-statistic = 43.7416 computed at lag 48 $< \chi_{0.05,45}^2 = 61.6562$ with a p-value of 0.5253. Using the residual ACF and PACF (Appendix XLV) up to lag 48 for a post mortem analysis, it was observed that just that just 2 of the coefficients (that is 0.1308 at lag 11 and 0.1364 at lag 35) in the ACF and 1 of the coefficients (that is 0.1273 at lag 11) in the PACF fall outside of the 95% confident interval $(-0.125, 0.125)$ which is less than 5% of the total number of lags.

Comparing the values of the various information criteria as shown in Appendices XIII and XIV respectively, it is noticed that the former model has lesser values compared to the later even though the difference is not much. The residual ACF and PACF and the p-value of the later model are better after all, but based on the principle of parsimony, the former model is entertained.

4.3 Cointegration Analysis

Using Johansen⁸⁴ (1991) cointegration technique to diagnose the long run relationship among these variables, empirical investigations show two cointegrating equations in trace test and maximum eigenvalue test at 5% significance level which imply that there exist long run relationships between the variables.

The two cointegrating equations are presented as

$$\begin{aligned} \ln COP = & 0.78512 - 0.0064767 \ln ER + 0.401914 \ln MC & (4.9) \\ & (0.454028) \quad (0.118516) \quad (0.0173925) \end{aligned}$$

$$\ln MC = -7.94212 + 1.72551 \ln COP + 1.87135 \ln ER \quad (4.10)$$

(0.793062) (0.07467) (0.213226)

Standard errors are presented in brackets below the coefficients.

There is evidence for a cointegrating relationship among the log of crude oil price, log of stock market capitalization and log of exchange rate since the unit-root hypothesis is not rejected for the individual variables as shown in Appendices I, II and V but the unit-root hypothesis is rejected for the residuals (\hat{u}) from the cointegrating regression as shown in Appendix XV. The respective test statistics $\tau_1 = -3.33505$ and $\tau_2 = 4.22178$ for the residuals of the two regression models above are less than the critical value $\tau = -2.88$ for $n = 235$ at 5% level of significance from the Empirical Cumulative Distribution of T for $\emptyset = 1$ Table.

The Johansen⁸⁴ (1991) cointegration test result is presented in the Appendix XV for logs of Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates relationship. The Johansen test results above suggest that there exist a viable, sustainable cum long run equilibrium relationships among all the variables in the system and this give us the hint that analyzing these variables as multivariate time series may yield a more robust result than analyzing them as univariates.

4.4 VAR Modelling

4.4.1 Model Identification

The optimal length selection criteria provide a basis for VAR model identification. The following information criteria prescribe optimal lag length for the VAR model of the log of Crude Oil Price, log of Stock Market Capitalization and log of Exchange Rate as follows:

$$AIC = 3, BIC = 2, \text{ and } HQ = 2$$

And the optimal lag length for the first differences of log of International Crude Oil Price, Nigerian Stock Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate as follows:

$$AIC = 2, BIC = 1, \text{ and } HQ = 1$$

The results of lag length structure test for the original variables and their logs are presented in the Appendices XVI and XVII respectively. Though the logs of the three series are not stationary, if the series are cointegrated, the resulting relationship will be stationary. This implies that using the first difference of the logs of the series may not be needful if the series are cointegrated since we may end up losing some vital information and also fitting a more complex model. VAR analysis is conducted with the logs of three series. The series are represented in a vector form as $\mathbf{X}'=[\ln\text{COP}, \ln\text{ER}, \ln\text{MC}]$

where $\ln\text{COP}$, $\ln\text{ER}$ and $\ln\text{MC}$ are the natural logs of Crude Oil Prices, Exchange Rates and the Market Capitalization respectively

From the above result, the tentative models are possibly any of these two VAR models;

$\text{VAR}(2)$ and $\text{VAR}(3)$.

4.4.2 Estimation of Model Parameters for $\text{VAR}(2)$

At lag length of $p = 2$, the inverse roots of the characteristic AR polynomial showed that $\text{VAR}(2)$ model presented in Appendix XVIII is stable since all the inverse roots lie inside of the unit circle as shown in Appendix XLVI. The $\text{VAR}(2)$ model is presented in matrix form as;

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{c} + \phi_1 \mathbf{X}_{t-1} + \phi_2 \mathbf{X}_{t-2} \quad (4.11)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{c} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.291 \\ (0.185) \\ [-1.574] \\ 0.034 \\ (0.035) \\ [0.947] \\ -0.419 \\ (0.175) \\ [-2.390] \end{bmatrix}, \phi_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.172 & 0.025 & 0.169 \\ (0.064) & (0.331) & (2.434) \\ [18.216] & [0.076] & [2.013] \\ -0.032 & 1.284 & -0.002 \\ (0.012) & (0.063) & (0.013) \\ [-2.605] & [20.247] & [-0.158] \\ 0.163 & -0.264 & 1.019 \\ (0.061) & (0.314) & (0.066) \\ [2.672] & [-0.841] & [15.477] \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{and } \phi_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.267 & 0.073 & -0.145 \\ (0.065) & (0.335) & (0.067) \\ [-4.106] & [0.218] & [-2.168] \\ 0.023 & -0.290 & 0.006 \\ (0.012) & (0.064) & (0.013) \\ [1.828] & [-4.509] & [0.478] \\ -0.091 & 0.374 & -0.067 \\ (0.062) & (0.319) & (0.063) \\ [-1.467] & [1.173] & [-1.005] \end{bmatrix}$$

Standard errors and t-ratios are respectively presented in brackets and square brackets below the coefficients. The information criteria are given as follows:

$AIC = -18.73$, $BIC = -18.43$ and $HQ = -18.61$; Portmanteau test statistic at lag 48, Q-statistic = 418.3984 with $p = 0.4304$. Adjusted Portmanteau test statistic at lag 48 = 465.2526 with $p = 0.0413$. The Portmanteau test critical value, $\chi^2_{0.05,414} = 462.44$. The Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test statistic at lag 48 = 186.0194 with $p = 0.3636$. The LM test critical value, $\chi^2_{0.05,180} = 212.304$.

4.4.3 Diagnostic Checking of the VAR(2) Model

Using the VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM test and the multivariate Portmanteau test as shown in Appendix XIX, it is seen that for VAR(2), the Q-statistic = 418.3984 at lag 48 $< \chi^2_{0.05,418} = 462.44$ with a probability value of $p = 0.4304$ and the adjusted Q-statistic = 465.2526 at lag 48 $> \chi^2_{0.05,414} = 462.44$ with a probability value of $p = 0.0413$. The LM statistic = 186.0194 at lag 20 $< \chi^2_{0.05,180} = 212.304$ with a probability value of $p = 0.2504$.

4.4.4 Estimation of Model Parameters for VAR(3)

At lag length of $p = 3$, the Inverse Roots of the characteristic AR polynomial showed that VAR(3) model presented in Appendix XX is stable since all the inverse roots lie inside of the unit circle as shown in Appendix XLVII. The VAR(3) model is presented in matrix form as;

$$\hat{X} = c + \phi_1 X_{t-1} + \phi_2 X_{t-2} + \phi_3 X_{t-3} \quad (4.12)$$

$$\text{where } c = \begin{bmatrix} -0.239 \\ (0.188) \\ [-1.274] \\ 0.010 \\ (0.035) \\ [0.297] \\ -0.392 \\ (0.179) \\ [-2.190] \end{bmatrix}, \phi_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.148 & -0.019 & 0.164 \\ (0.067) & (0.347) & (0.070) \\ [17.177] & [-0.056] & [2.359] \\ -0.021 & 1.310 & 0.000 \\ (0.012) & (0.064) & (0.013) \\ [-1.656] & [20.314] & [0.007] \\ 0.133 & -0.199 & 1.007 \\ (0.064) & (0.331) & (0.066) \\ [2.086] & [-0.602] & [15.162] \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\phi_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.140 & 0.350 & -0.160 \\ (0.101) & (0.555) & (0.099) \\ [-1.392] & [0.630] & [-1.613] \\ -0.027 & -0.444 & -0.008 \\ (0.019) & (0.103) & (0.018) \\ [-1.437] & [-4.308] & [-0.417] \\ 0.019 & 0.237 & 0.012 \\ (0.096) & (0.529) & (0.095) \\ [0.197] & [0.448] & [0.130] \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \phi_3 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.114 & -0.245 & 0.027 \\ (0.068) & (0.351) & (0.068) \\ [-1.681] & [-0.699] & [0.394] \\ 0.043 & 0.135 & 0.009 \\ (0.013) & (0.065) & (0.013) \\ [3.380] & [2.076] & [0.698] \\ -0.094 & 0.066 & -0.060 \\ (0.065) & (0.334) & (0.064) \\ [-1.459] & [0.198] & [-0.926] \end{bmatrix}$$

Standard errors and t-ratios are respectively presented in brackets and square brackets under the coefficients. The information criteria and other statistics are given as follows:

$AIC = -18.75$, $BIC = -18.31$ and $HQ = -18.58$; Portmanteau test statistic = 385.8216 with $p = 0.7458$. Adjusted Portmanteau test statistic = 431.0981 with $p = 0.1784$. The Portmanteau test critical value, $\chi_{0.05,405}^2 = 452.923$. The Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test statistic = 171.5225 with $p = 0.6623$. The LM test critical value, $\chi_{0.05,180}^2 = 212.304$.

4.4.5 Diagnostic Checking of the VAR (3) Model

For the VAR (3) model presented in Appendix XX, it is seen that the VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM test and the multivariate Portmanteau test as shown in Table 21 has a Q-statistic = 385.8216 at lag 48 $< \chi_{0.05,405}^2 = 452.923$ with a p-value of 0.7458 and the adjusted Q-statistic = 431.0981 at lag 48 $< \chi_{0.05,405}^2 = 452.923$ with a probability value of

$p = 0.1784$. The LM statistic = 171.5225 at lag 20 $< \chi_{0.05,180}^2 = 212.304$ with a probability value of $p = 0.6623$,

Comparing the VAR (2) and VAR (3) models, it is observed that there is no much difference among their information criteria. Although VAR (2) appears to have less values compared to the other, it is observed that VAR(2) has failed VAR Residual Serial Correlation Portmanteau test at the adjusted Q-statistic level. VAR (3) model is therefore entertained and it is used for analyzing the relationships between crude oil price, stock market capitalization and exchange rate.

4.4.6 Restricted VAR Parameters Estimation

Since some of the parameters of the respective models are not significantly different from zero, leaving them in the models may only increase the error component of the respective models. In order to checkmate this anomaly, restriction of the insignificant parameters from the model based on a threshold t-ratio value is carried out. This will not only help reduce the error component of the model, but will enhance achieving a far more robust result in terms of structural inference with the VAR models.

(a.) Restricted VAR (3) Parameters Estimation

Beginning with the VAR (3) model and with a benchmark t – ratio = 1.80, the following estimates are obtained;

$$\hat{X} = \hat{c} + \hat{\phi}_1 X_{t-1} + \hat{\phi}_2 X_{t-2} + \hat{\phi}_3 X_{t-3} \quad (4.13)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{c} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -0.022 \end{bmatrix}, \hat{\phi}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.959 & 0 & 0.021 \\ 0 & 1.367 & 0 \\ 0.090 & 0 & 0.960 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\hat{\phi}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.472 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \hat{\phi}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.002 & 0.107 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The information criteria and other statistics are given as follows:

$AIC = -18.62$, $BIC = -18.48$ and $HQ = -18.56$; Portmanteau test statistic = 461.0566 with $p = 0.1038$. Adjusted Portmanteau test statistic = 507.4691 with $p = 0.0033$. Appendix XX presents the Portmanteau test critical value as $\chi_{0.05,424}^2 = 473.009$.

The resulting relationship in linear form is given as

$$\ln COP_t = 0.959 \ln COP_{t-1} + 0.021 \ln MC_{t-1} \quad (4.14)$$

$$\ln ER_t = 1.367 \ln ER_{t-1} - 0.472 \ln ER_{t-2} + 0.107 \ln ER_{t-3} - 0.002 \ln COP_{t-3} \quad (4.15)$$

$$\ln MC_t = -0.022 + 0.960 \ln MC_{t-1} + 0.090 \ln COP_{t-1} \quad (4.16)$$

From the above relationships, it is noticed that all ER and MC depend on COP for predictability.

(b.) Diagnostic Checking of Restricted VAR (3) Model

VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM test cannot be performed with the restricted VAR(3) model since some of the matrices are not invertible as a result of the restrictions imposed on the VAR parameters. Using the multivariate Portmanteau test as shown in Appendix XXII, it is seen that for VAR(3) model with a benchmark t – ratio = 1.80 , the Q-statistic = 461.0566 at lag 48 $< \chi_{0.05,424}^2 = 473.009$ with a probability value of $p = 0.1038$ and the adjusted Q-statistic = 507.4691 at lag 48 $< \chi_{0.05,424}^2 = 473.009$ with a probability value of $p = 0.0033$.

(c.) Restricted VAR (2) Parameters Estimation

With the VAR (2) model and with a benchmark t – ratio = 1.80, the following estimates are obtained;

$$\hat{X} = \check{c} + \check{\phi}_1 X_{t-1} + \check{\phi}_2 X_{t-2} \quad (4.17)$$

$$\text{where } \check{c} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -0.023 \end{bmatrix}, \check{\phi}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.190 & 0 & 0.168 \\ -0.030 & 1.302 & 0 \\ 0.092 & 0 & 0.960 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{and } \check{\phi}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.252 & 0 & -0.137 \\ 0.027 & -0.299 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The information criteria and other statistics are given as follows:

$AIC = -18.69$, $BIC = -18.52$ and $HQ = -18.62$; Portmanteau test statistic = 426.6941 with $p = 0.4270$. Adjusted Portmanteau test statistic = 474.7638 with $p = 0.0385$. The Portmanteau test critical value, $\chi_{0.05,422}^2 = 470.895$. Appendix XXI presents the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test statistic = 191.4273 with $p = 0.2660$. The LM test critical value, $\chi_{0.05,180}^2 = 212.304$

The resulting relationship in linear form is given as

$$\ln COP_t = 1.190 \ln COP_{t-1} - 0.252 \ln COP_{t-2} + 0.168 \ln MC_{t-1} - 0.137 \ln MC_{t-2} \quad (4.18)$$

$$\ln ER_t = 1.302 \ln ER_{t-1} - 0.299 \ln ER_{t-2} - 0.030 \ln COP_{t-1} - 0.027 \ln COP_{t-2} \quad (4.19)$$

$$\ln MC_t = -0.023 + 0.960 \ln MC_{t-1} + 0.092 \ln COP_{t-1} \quad (4.20)$$

From the above relationships, it is noticed that all ER and MC depend on COP for predictability.

d. Diagnostic Checking of Restricted VAR (2) Model

Using the VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM test and the multivariate Portmanteau test as shown in Appendix XXIII, it is seen that for VAR(3) model with a benchmark t – ratio = 1.80 , the Q-statistic = 426.6941 at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,422}^2 = 470.895$ with a probability value of $p = 0.4270$ and the adjusted Q-statistic = 474.7638 at lag 48 < $\chi_{0.05,422}^2 = 470.895$ with a probability value of $p = 0.0385$. LM test statistic = 191.4273 at lag 20 < $\chi_{0.05,180}^2 = 212.304$ with a probability value of = 0.2660.

As a result the restrictions imposed on the VAR models; it is possible to clearly see which variable helps in better predicting others. The restrictions have also improved upon the significance of the models.

4.4.7 Structural Inference and Interpretation based on the VAR(3) Model

Granger-causality and instantaneous causality as presented in Appendix XXIV between the crude oil price, stock market capitalization and exchange rate were investigated based on this unrestricted VAR(3) model. From the Granger-causality test conducted, the null hypothesis of no Granger-causality from lnCOP to lnER, lnMC is rejected since the test

statistic $l = 5.0065 > F(6,663) = 2.11224$ at 5% significance level with a probability of null hypothesis, $p = 0.0000$. The null hypothesis of no Granger-causality from lnER to lnCOP, lnMC is accepted since the test statistic $l = 1.4856 < F(6,663) = 2.11224$ at 5% significance level with a probability of null hypothesis, $p = 0.1804$. We accept the null hypothesis of no Granger-causality from lnMC to lnCOP, lnER since the test statistic $l = 1.7455 < F(6,663) = 2.11224$ at 5% significance level with a probability of null hypothesis, $p = 0.1080$.

For instantaneous causality test, the null hypothesis of no instantaneous causality between lnCOP and lnER, lnMC is accepted since the test statistic $c = 2.4993 < \chi_{0.05,2}^2 = 5.99146$ at 5% level of significance with a probability of null hypothesis, $p = 0.2866$. The null hypothesis of no instantaneous causality between lnER and lnCOP, lnMC is accepted since the test statistic $c = 1.8153 < \chi_{0.05,2}^2 = 5.99146$ at 5% level of significance with a probability of null hypothesis, $p = 0.4034$. The null hypothesis of no instantaneous causality between lnMC and lnCOP, lnER is accepted since the test statistic $c = 0.8263 < \chi_{0.05,2}^2 = 5.99146$ at 5% level of significance with a probability of null hypothesis, $p = 0.6616$.

4.5 Forecasting

The adequacy of the models having been established and confirmed, a 2-step forecast lead having a forecast origin at $t = 239$ is obtained. The forecasts are presented in Appendices XLVIII, XLIX and L for the univariate models of log of Crude Oil Price in (4.1), log of Stock Market Capitalization in (4.5) and log of Exchange Rates in (4.7) respectively. The forecasts for the log of Crude Oil Price, log of Market Capitalization and log of Exchange Rates using the VAR(3) model are respectively presented in Appendices LI, LII and LIII. Appendices XXV and XXVI present the forecasts for logs of variables and the original variables respectively from univariate models, while Appendices XXVII and XXVIII present forecasts respectively for the logs of the variables and the original variables from the VAR model.

4.6 Discussion

Univariate time series models were fitted to the three time series variables (Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates). It was seen that the Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates respectively followed $ARIMA(0,1,1)$, $ARIMA(3,1,1)$ and $ARIMA(1,1,0)$ models.

Cointegration analysis was also used to diagnose the long run relationship among the three time series, it was discovered that the variables are cointegrated. Two cointegrating relationships exist among them. The existence of this long run relationship implies that a change in one of these variables (especially the one with predictive power) will tantamount to a change in the others. The establishment of the long run relationship gives us a ground to model the three variables as multivariate.

The variables were analyzed as multivariate time series and a vector autoregressive model of order three ($VAR(3)$ model) was prescribed for the VAR analysis. The model was seen to be adequate as the inverse root of the characteristic polynomial confirms that the VAR has met the stability condition. The multivariate Portmanteau test and the VAR Residual Serial Correlation also confirm the adequacy of the model since the Q-statistic = 385.8216 at lag 48 $< \chi^2_{0.05,405} = 452.923$ with a p-value of 0.7458 and the adjusted Q-statistic = 431.0981 at lag 48 $< \chi^2_{0.05,405} = 452.923$ with a probability value of $p = 0.1784$. The LM statistic = 171.5225 at lag 20 $< \chi^2_{0.05,180} = 212.304$ with a probability value of $p = 0.6623$, (Table 19). The various information criteria also speak well of the model.

The $VAR(3)$ model was used to make structural inferences in terms of Granger-Causality and instantaneous causality on the relationships between the time series variables. From the Granger-causality test conducted, the null hypothesis of no Granger-causality from \lnCOP to \lnER , \lnMC was rejected and the null hypothesis of no Granger-causality from \lnER to \lnCOP was accepted, and also the null hypothesis of no Granger-causality from \lnMC to \lnCOP , \lnER was accepted. For instantaneous causality test, the null hypothesis of no instantaneous causality from \lnCOP to \lnER , \lnMC was accepted, the null hypothesis of no

instantaneous causality from $\ln ER$ to $\ln COP$, $\ln MC$ was accepted, and the null hypothesis of no instantaneous causality from $\ln MC$ to $\ln COP$, $\ln ER$ was also accepted. These results imply that the distortions in the Crude Oil Prices will cause effect(s) in the Exchange Rates and Market Capitalization though these effects may not be instantaneous; that is, the effects may be obvious after some time lags. Distortions in Exchange Rates does not cause any effect in Crude Oil Prices and Market Capitalization both instantaneously and in the long run. Movement in the Market Capitalization does not cause any effect in Crude Oil Prices and Exchange Rates both instantaneously and in the long run. The result is a hint to the authority and policy makers to keep a watch on the distortions on the prices of crude oil in order to be guided on improving the indicators of economic growth and the stock market.

The univariate models and the $VAR(3)$ model were then used to compute a two time lead forecasts. The results from the $VAR(3)$ showed a decrease in the Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization but an increase in the Exchange Rates (in Dollar). The results from the univariate models showed a decrease in the Crude Oil Price and Market Capitalization but an increase in the Exchange Rate (USD). Comparing the forecasts from the VAR model and the univariate models, it could be inferred that the VAR presents a better framework for forecasting the time series because comparing the real life data with the forecasts; they fall within the confidence limits of the forecasts.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

A nexus between the crude oil prices, Nigerian stock market indices and the economic growth was investigated using vector autoregressive (VAR) model and cointegration analysis. The Market Capitalization was used as proxy for the Nigerian stock market indices while Exchange Rate was used as proxy for the economic growth. In exploring these relationships, various steps and aspects were pre-investigated in making sure that the relationships among these variables are properly perused.

Firstly, univariate time series modelling of the three component time series variables was carried out and it was seen that the logs of Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates respectively followed ARIMA(0,1,1), ARIMA(3,1,1) and ARIMA(1,1,0) models.

Cointegration analysis was also used to diagnose the long run relationship among the variables. From the results obtained, there exists a long run, viable cum sustainable equilibrium among these variables. This provided a solid ground for the analysis of these three economic variables as multivariate.

In analyzing the series as multivariate time series using vector autoregressive (VAR) model, a VAR(3) model was seen to be adequate in capturing the dynamic relationship amongst the series.

The VAR(3) model was used for structural analysis as shown in Table 21. Granger-causality test result showed that $\ln\text{COP}$ Granger-causes $\ln\text{ER}$, $\ln\text{MC}$; $\ln\text{ER}$ does not Granger-cause $\ln\text{COP}$, $\ln\text{MC}$; and $\ln\text{MC}$ does not Granger-cause $\ln\text{COP}$, $\ln\text{ER}$. Instantaneous causality test result showed that there is no instantaneous causality between the time series variables which imply that a change in one of the variables may not really trigger or cause changes in the other two variables immediately.

Finally, the VAR(3) model was used to compute a two-step ahead (December 2014 to January 2015) forecasts from the origin $t = 239$. The univariate time series models (4.1, 4.5

and 4.7) were also used to compute a two-step ahead (December 2014 to January 2015) forecasts from the origin $t = 239$. The results showed a decrease in the Crude Oil Price and Market Capitalization but an increase in the Exchange Rates (in Dollar). Comparing the forecasts from the VAR model and the univariate models, it could be inferred that the VAR presents a better framework for forecasting the time series because comparing the real life data with the forecasts; they fall with the confidence limits of the forecasts.

5.2 Conclusion

Conclusively, in modelling the logs of Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rate as univariates, the adequate representation of the variables based on the results obtained from this study are $ARIMA(0,1,1)$, $ARIMA(3,1,1)$ and $ARIMA(1,1,0)$ models. From the cointegration analysis results, it was noticed that there exists a sustainable equilibrium among the series. Since dynamic relationships exist between the variables, there was a need to model the variables as multivariate. In modelling the relationships among logs of Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates, a $VAR(3)$ model was seen to be appropriate in capturing the dynamic interdependencies that exist among them. The forecasts showed that the VAR model presents a better framework for forecasting the time series since the forecasts are very close to the real life values for the respective variables except for crude oil possibly due to the inability of the market capitalization and exchange rate to Granger-cause crude oil price.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on this work, the following recommendations were made:

- (i) The presence of a long run relationship among the international crude oil price, the Nigerian stock market indices and the economic growth suggests that the volume of the market indices and economic indicators are highly sensitive to the distortions in the international crude oil prices and as such, investors and stock brokers in the stock market should be guided by the movement in the oil prices on their investment decisions. Policy makers should keep their eyes on the trend in the global oil prices so as to formulate more

pragmatic policies that will positively impact on the stock market returns in particular and the entire economy in general.

(ii) In modelling these economic variables as univariates, it is recommended that *ARIMA(0,1,1)*, *ARIMA(3,1,1)* and *ARIMA(1,1,0)* models be adopted for logs of Crude Oil Price, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates respectively as they have been confirmed to fit the variables adequately.

(iii) In order to obtain better forecasts for the three time series variables, it is recommended that the variables should be modeled as multivariate since there exist a dynamic, sustainable and equilibrium relationship among them and a *VAR(3)* model is confirmed to be very adequate for the analysis. Cointegration analysis also confirming the existence of a long run relation among the variables.

Contributions

This research work has been able to contribute to the body of knowledge in the following ways;

- i. Contextually, it has been able to deviate from the previous works in the subject area in terms of variables involved. Most of them (Adaramola, 2012; Jones and Kaul, 1996, and Sadorsky, 1999) which investigates the impact of the international crude oil price on a particular stock market index like stock returns. This study focuses on the analyzing the relationships that exist between the crude oil price, stock market indicators and the economic growth using Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates (in dollars) as proxies for stock market indicators and economic growth respectively.
- ii. Methodologically, this research has been able to develop time series models for analyzing the relationships that exist between Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates and also provide a forecasting framework for the said variables.
- iii. And practically, it points to the fact the better forecasts for this time series variables can best be obtained when modelling them as multivariate than when modelling them as univariates.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: Unit Root Test on Log of Crude Oil Prices

Null Hypothesis: LG_CRUDEOILPRICES has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=14)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.407061	0.5786
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.457865	
5% level	-2.873543	
10% level	-2.573242	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Appendix II: Unit Root Test on Log of Crude Oil Prices at First Difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LG_CRUDEOILPRICES) has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=14)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-11.92460	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.457865	
5% level	-2.873543	
10% level	-2.573242	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Appendix III: Unit Root Test on Log of Market Capitalization

Null Hypothesis: LG_MARKETCAPITILATION has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=14)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.292262	0.6336
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.457747	
5% level	-2.873492	
10% level	-2.573215	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Appendix IV: Unit Root Test on Log of Market Capitalization at First Difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LG_MARKETCAPITILATION) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=14)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-13.60999	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.457865	
5% level	-2.873543	
10% level	-2.573242	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Appendix V: Unit Root Test on Log of Exchange Rates

Null Hypothesis: LG_EXCHANGERATES has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=14)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.102509	0.7152
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.457865	
5% level	-2.873543	
10% level	-2.573242	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Appendix VI: Unit Root Test on Log of Exchange Rates at First Difference

Null Hypothesis: D(LG_EXCHANGERATES) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=14)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-10.81530	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.457865	
5% level	-2.873543	
10% level	-2.573242	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Appendix VII: ARIMA (0,1,1) Model of (4.1)

Model 1: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_CrudeOilPrices

Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
theta_1	0.206412	0.0572169	3.6075	0.00031	***

Mean dependent var	0.006031		S.D. dependent var	0.081328
Mean of innovations	0.004937		S.D. of innovations	0.079301
Log-likelihood	265.4817		Akaike criterion	-526.9633
Schwarz criterion	-520.0188		Hannan-Quinn	-524.1645

Appendix VIII: ARIMA (0,1,2) Model of (4.2)

Model 2: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_CrudeOilPrices

Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
theta_1	0.226918	0.0639964	3.5458	0.00039	***
theta_2	0.129314	0.0652255	1.9826	0.04742	**

Mean dependent var	0.006031		S.D. dependent var	0.081328
Mean of innovations	0.004317		S.D. of innovations	0.078665
Log-likelihood	267.3838		Akaike criterion	-528.7677
Schwarz criterion	-518.3509		Hannan-Quinn	-524.5695

Appendix IX: ARIMA (0,1,25) Model of (4.3)

Model 3: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_CrudeOilPrices

Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
theta_1	0.228619	0.0556607	4.1074	0.00004	***
theta_13	-0.172449	0.0652704	-2.6421	0.00824	***
theta_25	0.161393	0.0619959	2.6033	0.00923	***

Mean dependent var	0.006031		S.D. dependent var	0.081328
Mean of innovations	0.004949		S.D. of innovations	0.077022
Log-likelihood	271.8205		Akaike criterion	-535.6411
Schwarz criterion	-521.7520		Hannan-Quinn	-530.0435

Appendix X: ARIMA (0,1,25) Model of (4.4)

Model 4: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_CrudeOilPrices

Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
theta_1	0.259009	0.0629187	4.1166	0.00004	***
theta_2	0.144084	0.0648282	2.2226	0.02625	**
theta_13	-0.151655	0.0629627	-2.4087	0.01601	**
theta_25	0.176655	0.0608958	2.9009	0.00372	***

Mean dependent var	0.006031		S.D. dependent var	0.081328
Mean of innovations	0.004121		S.D. of innovations	0.076241
Log-likelihood	274.1941		Akaike criterion	-538.3882
Schwarz criterion	-521.0268		Hannan-Quinn	-531.3913

Appendix XI: ARIMA (3,1,1) Model of (4.5)

Model 5: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_MarketCapitalization

Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
phi_1	-0.415256	0.147264	-2.8198	0.00481	***
phi_2	0.205144	0.0703925	2.9143	0.00357	***
phi_3	0.314919	0.0614626	5.1237	<0.00001	***
theta_1	0.578498	0.149982	3.8571	0.00011	***

Mean dependent var	0.021601		S.D. dependent var	0.076071
Mean of innovations	0.012084		S.D. of innovations	0.073537
Log-likelihood	283.2847		Akaike criterion	-556.5694
Schwarz criterion	-539.2080		Hannan-Quinn	-549.5724

Appendix XII: ARIMA (13,1,29) Model of (4.6)

Model 6: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_MarketCapitalization

Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
const	0.0213894	0.00337635	6.3351	<0.00001	***
phi_4	-0.159927	0.064227	-2.4900	0.01277	**
phi_13	-0.131656	0.0639956	-2.0573	0.03966	**
theta_3	0.237947	0.0623344	3.8173	0.00013	***
theta_25	-0.161123	0.0684053	-2.3554	0.01850	**
theta_29	-0.166021	0.0630905	-2.6315	0.00850	***

Mean dependent var	0.021601		S.D. dependent var	0.076071
Mean of innovations	0.000814		S.D. of innovations	0.070435
Log-likelihood	292.6530		Akaike criterion	-571.3059
Schwarz criterion	-547.0000		Hannan-Quinn	-561.5102

Appendix XIII: ARIMA (1,1,0) Model of (4.7)

Model 7: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)

Dependent variable: (1-L) l_ExchangeRates
Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
phi_1	0.354428	0.0606021	5.8484	<0.00001	***

Mean dependent var	0.002918		S.D. dependent var	0.015729
Mean of innovations	0.001909		S.D. of innovations	0.014925
Log-likelihood	662.9456		Akaike criterion	-1321.891
Schwarz criterion	-1314.947		Hannan-Quinn	-1319.092

Appendix XIV: ARIMA (1,1,2) Model of (4.8)

Model 8: ARIMA, using observations 1995:02-2014:11 (T = 238)
Dependent variable: (1-L) l_ExchangeRates
Standard errors based on Hessian

	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
phi_1	-0.754687	0.226068	-3.3383	0.00084	***
theta_1	1.14785	0.223689	5.1315	<0.00001	***
theta_2	0.347507	0.0889898	3.9050	0.00009	***

Mean dependent var	0.002918		S.D. dependent var	0.015729
Mean of innovations	0.002074		S.D. of innovations	0.014821
Log-likelihood	664.5894		Akaike criterion	-1321.179
Schwarz criterion	-1307.290		Hannan-Quinn	-1315.581

Appendix XV: Johansen Cointegration Test Showing 2 Cointegration Relationship among the Variables

Sample (adjusted): 1995M05 2014M11

Included observations: 235 after adjustments

Trend assumption: No deterministic trend

Series: LG_CRUDEOILPRICES LG_EXCHANGERATES
 LG_MARKETCAPITILATION
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 3

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.085945	37.71440	24.27596	0.0006
At most 1 *	0.067685	16.59631	12.32090	0.0091
At most 2	0.000538	0.126505	4.129906	0.7694

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.085945	21.11810	17.79730	0.0152
At most 1 *	0.067685	16.46980	11.22480	0.0055
At most 2	0.000538	0.126505	4.129906	0.7694

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Cointegrating regression

OLS, using observations 1995:01-2014:11 (T = 239)

Dependent variable: I_COP

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	0.785120	0.454028	1.729	0.0851 *
I_ER	-0.00647617	0.118516	-0.05464	0.9565
I_MC	0.401914	0.0173925	23.11	1.55e-062 ***

Mean dependent var 3.767689 S.D. dependent var 0.668680
 Sum squared resid 8.942273 S.E. of regression 0.194656
 R-squared 0.915970 Adjusted R-squared 0.915258
 Log-likelihood 53.51170 Akaike criterion -101.0234
 Schwarz criterion -90.59400 Hannan-Quinn -96.82064
 rho 0.907080 Durbin-Watson 0.186810

Testing for a unit root in uhat (the residuals) for the regression of I_COP on I_ER & I_MC

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for uhat
 including 3 lags of (1-L)uhat
 sample size 235
 unit-root null hypothesis: a = 1

model: $(1-L)y = (a-1)*y(-1) + \dots + e$
 1st-order autocorrelation coeff. for e: 0.000
 lagged differences: $F(3, 231) = 3.680$ [0.0128]
 estimated value of $(a - 1)$: -0.128083
 test statistic: $\tau_c(3) = -4.22178$
 asymptotic p-value 0.01255

Dependent variable: I_MC

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	-7.94212	0.793062	-10.01	6.68e-020 ***
I_COP	1.72551	0.0746700	23.11	1.55e-062 ***
I_ER	1.87135	0.213226	8.776	3.46e-016 ***

Mean dependent var 7.497876 S.D. dependent var 1.595663
 Sum squared resid 38.39122 S.E. of regression 0.403329
 R-squared 0.936646 Adjusted R-squared 0.936109
 Log-likelihood -120.6044 Akaike criterion 247.2089
 Schwarz criterion 257.6383 Hannan-Quinn 251.4117
 rho 0.926802 Durbin-Watson 0.146560

Testing for a unit root in uhat (the residuals) for the regression of I_MC on I_COP & I_ER

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for uhat
 including 3 lags of $(1-L)uhat$
 sample size 235
 unit-root null hypothesis: $a = 1$

model: $(1-L)y = (a-1)*y(-1) + \dots + e$
 1st-order autocorrelation coeff. for e: 0.001
 lagged differences: $F(3, 231) = 1.438$ [0.2324]
 estimated value of $(a - 1)$: -0.0892779
 test statistic: $\tau_c(3) = -3.33505$
 asymptotic p-value 0.1286

Dependent variable: I_ER

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	3.79813	0.0429836	88.36	7.59e-183 ***
I_COP	-0.001954	0.0357523	-0.05464	0.9565
I_MC	0.131491	0.0149824	8.776	3.46e-016 ***

Mean dependent var 4.776672 S.D. dependent var 0.234167
 Sum squared resid 2.697581 S.E. of regression 0.106913
 R-squared 0.793297 Adjusted R-squared 0.791545
 Log-likelihood 196.7246 Akaike criterion -387.4492
 Schwarz criterion -377.0198 Hannan-Quinn -383.2464
 rho 0.983049 Durbin-Watson 0.033820

Testing for a unit root in uhat (the residuals) for the regression of I_ER on I_COP & I_MC

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for uhat
 including 3 lags of $(1-L)uhat$

sample size 235

unit-root null hypothesis: $a = 1$

model: $(1-L)y = (a-1)*y(-1) + \dots + e$

1st-order autocorrelation coeff. for e: 0.008

lagged differences: $F(3, 231) = 10.916 [0.0000]$

estimated value of $(a - 1)$: -0.0252699

test statistic: $\tau_c(3) = -2.2106$

asymptotic p-value 0.6348

There is evidence for a cointegrating relationship if:

(a) The unit-root hypothesis is not rejected for the individual variables.

(b) The unit-root hypothesis is rejected for the residuals (\hat{u}) from the cointegrating regression.

Appendix XVI: Optimal Lag Length Selection for the Log of the Variables

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria						
Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-185.9123	NA	0.001030	1.635604	1.680311	1.653636
1	1175.944	2676.548	8.43e-09	-10.07743	-9.898608	-10.00531
2	1201.086	48.76155	7.33e-09	-10.21720	-9.904251*	-10.09098*
3	1211.439	19.80896*	7.25e-09*	-10.22891*	-9.781842	-10.04859
4	1217.518	11.47412	7.44e-09	-10.20362	-9.622434	-9.969208
* indicates lag order selected by the criterion						

Appendix XVII: Optimal Lag Length Selection for the Difference of the Log of the Variables

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria				

Endogenous variables: DF_LG_CRUDEOILPRICES DF_LG_EXCHANGERATES DF_LG_MARKETCAPITILATION						
Exogenous variables: C						
Sample: 1995M01 2014M11						
Included observations: 230						
Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	1149.029	NA	9.43e-09	-9.965473	-9.920629	-9.947384
1	1179.214	59.31849	7.85e-09	-10.14968	- 9.970306*	- 10.07733*
2	1191.714	24.23982 *	7.61e-09*	- 10.18012*	-9.866210	-10.05350
3	1198.803	13.56149	7.74e-09	-10.16350	-9.715059	-9.982610
4	1205.610	12.84547	7.89e-09	-10.14444	-9.561460	-9.909277
5	1209.923	8.025425	8.22e-09	-10.10368	-9.386168	-9.814250
6	1216.278	11.65972	8.42e-09	-10.08068	-9.228633	-9.736980
7	1218.936	4.806684	8.90e-09	-10.02553	-9.038947	-9.627560
8	1222.788	6.866956	9.31e-09	-9.980763	-8.859650	-9.528529
* indicates lag order selected by the criterion						
LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)						
FPE: Final prediction error						
AIC: Akaike information criterion						
SC: Schwarz information criterion						
HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion						

Appendix XVIII: VAR (2) Estimation Results

Vector Autoregression Estimates	
Date: 07/30/15 Time: 20:05	

Sample (adjusted): 1995M03 2014M11			
Included observations: 237 after adjustments			
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []			
	LG_CRUDE OILPRICES	LG_EXCHA NGERATES	LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION
LG_CRUDEOILPR ICES(-1)	1.172700	-0.031781	0.163837
	(0.06418)	(0.01232)	(0.06098)
	[18.2723]	[-2.57901]	[2.68669]
LG_CRUDEOILPR ICES(-2)	-0.267072	0.022910	-0.090548
	(0.06492)	(0.01247)	(0.06168)
	[-4.11398]	[1.83796]	[-1.46794]
LG_EXCHANGER ATES(-1)	0.026681	1.286182	-0.262306
	(0.32996)	(0.06336)	(0.31352)
	[0.08086]	[20.3008]	[-0.83665]
LG_EXCHANGER ATES(-2)	0.071477	-0.291766	0.371696
	(0.33446)	(0.06422)	(0.31779)
	[0.21371]	[-4.54325]	[1.16962]
LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION(-1)	0.168580	-0.002275	1.019093
	(0.06916)	(0.01328)	(0.06571)
	[2.43765]	[-0.17135]	[15.5087]
LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION(-2)	-0.144814	0.006069	-0.067023
	(0.06663)	(0.01279)	(0.06331)
	[-2.17333]	[0.47433]	[-1.05861]
C	-0.290258	0.034008	-0.418762
	(0.18427)	(0.03538)	(0.17509)
	[-1.57520]	[0.96117]	[-2.39176]
R-squared	0.987107	0.996085	0.997927
Adj. R-squared	0.986770	0.995983	0.997873
Sum sq. resids	1.352804	0.049876	1.221347
S.E. equation	0.076693	0.014726	0.072871
F-statistic	2934.801	9753.216	18454.70
Log likelihood	275.8684	666.9655	287.9821
Akaike AIC	-2.268932	-5.569329	-2.371157
Schwarz SC	-2.166500	-5.466897	-2.268725
Mean dependent	3.774951	4.779983	7.522209
S.D. dependent	0.666777	0.232341	1.580081
Determinant resid covariance (dof)		6.63E-09	

adj.)		
Determinant resid covariance	6.06E-09	
Log likelihood	1233.352	

Appendix XIX: VAR(2) Residual Serial Autocorrelation Test

PORTMANTEAU TEST ($H_0: \rho_h = (\rho_1, \dots, \rho_h) = 0$)

Reference: Lütkepohl (1993), Introduction to Multiple Time Series Analysis, 2ed, p. 150.

tested order: 48
test statistic: 422.1057
p-value: 0.3809
adjusted test statistic: 470.6576
p-value: 0.0282
degrees of freedom: 414.0000

LM-TYPE TEST FOR AUTOCORRELATION with 20 lags

Reference: Doornik (1996), LM test and LMF test (with F-approximation)

LM statistic: 173.4429
p-value: 0.6235
df: 180.0000
LMF statistic: 0.9163
p-value: 0.7533
df1: 180.0000
df2: 489.0000

Vector Autoregression Estimates			
Date: 07/30/15		Time: 20:14	
Sample (adjusted): 1995M04 2014M11			
Included observations: 236 after adjustments			
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []			
	LG_CRUDEOIL PRICES	LG_EXCHANG ERATES	LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION
LG_CRUDEOILPR ICES(-1)	1.148976 (0.06685) [17.1869]	-0.020962 (0.01250) [-1.67709]	0.133346 (0.06356) [2.09801]
LG_CRUDEOILPR ICES(-2)	-0.138397 (0.10079) [-1.37314]	-0.027537 (0.01884) [-1.46129]	0.019748 (0.09582) [0.20608]
LG_CRUDEOILPR ICES(-3)	-0.113317 (0.06780) [-1.67128]	0.042332 (0.01268) [3.33934]	-0.093907 (0.06446) [-1.45677]
LG_EXCHANGER ATES(-1)	0.001627 (0.34686) [0.00469]	1.302340 (0.06485) [20.0823]	-0.189526 (0.32977) [-0.57473]
LG_EXCHANGER ATES(-2)	0.335634 (0.55559) [0.60411]	-0.439330 (0.10388) [-4.22940]	0.230597 (0.52821) [0.43656]
LG_EXCHANGER ATES(-3)	-0.252635 (0.35075) [-0.72028]	0.137771 (0.06558) [2.10089]	0.062775 (0.33347) [0.18825]
LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION(-1)	0.165534 (0.06973) [2.37404]	-0.000283 (0.01304) [-0.02174]	1.007298 (0.06629) [15.1950]
LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION(-2)	-0.162613 (0.09926) [-1.63819]	-0.006804 (0.01856) [-0.36664]	0.011129 (0.09437) [0.11793]
LG_MARKETCAPI TILATION(-3)	0.026290	0.008876	-0.059776

	(0.06759)	(0.01264)	(0.06426)
	[0.38899]	[0.70241]	[-0.93028]
C	-0.235598	0.009127	-0.390092
	(0.18779)	(0.03511)	(0.17854)
	[-1.25460]	[0.25995]	[-2.18495]
R-squared	0.987210	0.996302	0.997928
Adj. R-squared	0.986700	0.996155	0.997845
Sum sq. resids	1.332606	0.046583	1.204534
S.E. equation	0.076789	0.014357	0.073005
F-statistic	1938.193	6765.073	12091.99
Log likelihood	275.9806	671.7131	287.9037
Akaike AIC	-2.254073	-5.607738	-2.355116
Schwarz SC	-2.107300	-5.460965	-2.208343
Mean dependent	3.778574	4.781586	7.534151
S.D. dependent	0.665852	0.231518	1.572686
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		6.39E-09	
Determinant resid covariance		5.61E-09	
Log likelihood		1237.282	

Appendix XXI: VAR(3) Residual Serial Autocorrelation Test

PORTMANTEAU TEST ($H_0: R_h = (r_1, \dots, r_h) = 0$)

Reference: Lütkepohl (1993), Introduction to Multiple Time Series Analysis, 2ed, p. 150.

tested order: 48
test statistic: 390.2033
p-value: 0.6925
adjusted test statistic: 437.2242
p-value: 0.1299
degrees of freedom: 405.0000

LM-TYPE TEST FOR AUTOCORRELATION with 20 lags

Reference: Doornik (1996), LM test and LMF test (with F-approximation)

LM statistic: 169.5617
p-value: 0.7005
df: 180.0000
LMF statistic: 0.8684
p-value: 0.8662
df1: 180.0000
df2: 477.0000

Appendix XXII: Restricted VAR(3) Residual Serial Autocorrelation Test at $t = 1.80$

PORTMANTEAU TEST ($H_0: R_h = (r_1, \dots, r_h) = 0$)

Reference: Lütkepohl (1993), Introduction to Multiple Time Series Analysis, 2ed, p. 150.

tested order: 48
test statistic: 461.0566
p-value: 0.1038
adjusted test statistic: 507.4691
p-value: 0.0033
degrees of freedom: 424.0000

VAR MODEL STATISTICS

Log Likelihood: 1.171076e+03
Determinant (Cov): 7.586433e-09

AIC: -1.861898e+01
FPE: 8.201262e-09
SC: -1.848486e+01
HQ: -1.856489e+01

Appendix XXIII: Restricted VAR(2) Residual Serial Autocorrelation Test at $t = 1.80$

PORTMANTEAU TEST ($H_0: R_h = (r_1, \dots, r_h) = 0$)

Reference: Lütkepohl (1993), Introduction to Multiple Time Series Analysis, 2ed, p. 150.

tested order: 48
test statistic: 426.6941
p-value: 0.4270
adjusted test statistic: 474.7638
p-value: 0.0385
degrees of freedom: 422.0000

LM-TYPE TEST FOR AUTOCORRELATION with 20 lags

Reference: Doornik (1996), LM test and LMF test (with F-approximation)

LM statistic: 191.4273
p-value: 0.2660
df: 180.0000

LMF statistic not computed for subset model.

VAR MODEL STATISTICS

Log Likelihood: 1.191142e+03
Determinant (Cov): 6.966912e-09

AIC: -1.868727e+01
FPE: 7.659966e-09
SC: -1.852384e+01
HQ: -1.862136e+01

Appendix XXIV: Causality Test Results

TEST FOR GRANGER-CAUSALITY:

H0: "LCrudeOilPrices_log" do not Granger-cause "LExchangeRates_log, LMarketCapt_log"

Test statistic $l = 5.0065$
pval-F(1; 6, 663) = 0.0000

TEST FOR INSTANTANEOUS CAUSALITY:

H0: No instantaneous causality between "LCrudeOilPrices_log" and "LExchangeRates_log, LMarketCapt_log"

Test statistic: $c = 2.4993$
pval-Chi(c; 2) = 0.2866

TEST FOR GRANGER-CAUSALITY:

H0: "LExchangeRates_log" do not Granger-cause "LCrudeOilPrices_log, LMarketCapt_log"

Test statistic $l = 1.4856$
pval-F(1; 6, 663) = 0.1804

TEST FOR INSTANTANEOUS CAUSALITY:

H0: No instantaneous causality between "LExchangeRates_log" and "LCrudeOilPrices_log, LMarketCapt_log"

Test statistic: $c = 1.8153$
pval-Chi(c; 2) = 0.4035

TEST FOR GRANGER-CAUSALITY:

H0: "LMarketCapt_log" do not Granger-cause "LCrudeOilPrices_log, LExchangeRates_log"

Test statistic $l = 1.7455$
pval-F(1; 6, 663) = 0.1080

TEST FOR INSTANTANEOUS CAUSALITY:

H0: No instantaneous causality between "LMarketCapt_log" and "LCrudeOilPrices_log, LExchangeRates_log"

Test statistic: $c = 0.8263$
pval-Chi(c; 2) = 0.6616

Appendix XXV: 2-Point Forecast Values for the Log of Variables from the Univariate Models

For 95% confidence intervals, $z(0.025) = 1.96$

Obs	l_COP	prediction	std. error	95% interval
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2014:12	undefined	4.30978	0.0793014	(4.15436, 4.46521)
2015:01	undefined	4.30978	0.124264	(4.06623, 4.55334)
Obs	l_MC	prediction	std. error	95% interval
2014:12	undefined	9.71646	0.0735365	(9.57233, 9.86059)
2015:01	undefined	9.69449	0.112804	(9.47340, 9.91558)
Obs	l_ER	prediction	std. error	95% interval
2014:12	undefined	5.08118	0.0149252	(5.05193, 5.11044)
2015:01	undefined	5.08331	0.0251279	(5.03406, 5.13256)

Appendix XXVI: 2-Point Forecast Values for the Original Variables from the Univariate Models

Observation	COP Forecast	95% interval
2014:12	74.424	(63.711, 86.939)
2015:01	74.424	(58.337, 94.949)
Observation	MC Forecast	95% interval
2014:12	16588.418	(14361.840, 19160.191)
2015:01	16227.944	(13009.043, 20243.317)
Observation	ER Forecast	95% interval
2014:12	160.974	(156.327, 165.743)
2015:01	161.307	(153.555, 169.450)

Appendix XXVII: 2-Point Forecast Values for the Log of Variables from the VAR(3) Model

For 95% confidence intervals, $t(226, 0.025) = 1.971$

Obs	l_COP	prediction	std. error	95% interval
-----	-------	------------	------------	--------------

2014:12	undefined	4.31638	0.0751441	(4.16831, 4.46446)
2015:01	undefined	4.33550	0.115654	(4.10760, 4.56340)
Obs	l_MC	prediction	std. error	95% interval
2014:12	undefined	9.69723	0.0714420	(9.55645, 9.83800)
2015:01	undefined	9.66881	0.102470	(9.46689, 9.87072)
Obs	l_ER	prediction	std. error	95% interval
2014:12	undefined	5.09052	0.0140494	(5.06284, 5.11821)
2015:01	undefined	5.10190	0.0232442	(5.05610, 5.14770)

Appendix XXVIII: 2-Point Forecast Values for the Original Variables from the VAR(3) Model

Observation	COP Forecast	95% interval
2014:12	74.917	(64.606, 86.874)
2015:01	76.363	(60.801, 95.909)
Observation	MC Forecast	95% interval
2014:12	21316.357	(14135.576, 18732.214)
2015:01	15816.516	(12924.629, 19355.270)
Observation	ER Forecast	95% interval
2014:12	162.474	(158.039, 167.036)
2015:01	164.334	(153.555, 172.035)

Appendix XXIX: Time Series Plots of Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates

Appendix XXX: Time Series Plots of Log of Crude Oil Prices, Market Capitalization and Exchange Rates

Appendix XXXI: ACF and PACF of the Log of Crude Oil Prices at Levels

Appendix XXXII: ACF and PACF of the Log of Market Capitalization at Levels

Appendix XXXIII: ACF and PACF of the Log of Exchange Rates at Levels

Appendix XXXIV: Time Series Plots of the Difference of the Log of the Three Series

Appendix XXXV: ACF and PACF of the Difference of the Log of Crude Oil Price

Appendix XXXVI: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (0,1,1) model in (4.1)

Appendix XXXVII: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (0,1,2) model in (4.2)

Appendix XXXVIII: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (0,1,25) model in (4.3)

Appendix XXXIX: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (0,1,25) model in (4.4)

Appendix XL: ACF and PACF of the difference of the log of Market Capitalization

Appendix XLI: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (3,1,1) model in (4.5)

Appendix XLII: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (13,1,29) model in (4.6)

Appendix XLIII: ACF and PACF of the difference of the log of Exchange Rates

Appendix XLIV: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (1,1,0) model in (4.7)

Appendix XLV: Residual ACF and PACF of the ARIMA (1,1,2) model in (4.8)

Appendix XLVI: Stability of VAR(2) Model

VAR inverse roots in relation to the unit circle

Appendix XLVII: Stability of VAR (3) Model

VAR inverse roots in relation to the unit circle

Appendix XLVIII: 2 Point Forecasts of log of Crude Oil Prices from ARIMA (0,1,1) in (4.1)

Appendix XLIX: 2 Point Forecasts of log of Market Capitalization from ARIMA (3,1,1) in (4.5)

Appendix L: 2 Point Forecasts of log of Exchange Rates from ARIMA (1,1,0) in (4.7)

Appendix LI: 2 Point Forecasts of the log of Crude Oil Prices from the VAR (3) Model

Appendix LII: 2 Point Forecasts of the log of Market Capitalization from the VAR (3) Model

Appendix LIII: 2 Point Forecasts of the log of Exchange Rates from the VAR (3) Model

